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FAIRCORE4EOSC Components Beta Release Report

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Deliverable Abstract

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project started in June 2022 and will deliver nine new EOSC-Core components in support of a FAIR research life cycle, bridging the gaps identified in the EOSC SRIA. More specifically, the components will enable an EOSC PID infrastructure, an EOSC research software infrastructure, support for sharing and access to metadata schemas and crosswalks and offer advanced research-intent driven discovery services over all EOSC repositories.

This deliverable summarises the technical status of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components and the functionalities available in the Beta Release (M18). The report is based on the input received by WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 via the milestones at M16. Next to an overview of the technical status it also provides an overview of the project high-level roadmap, the status of requirements and the planned activities in terms of integration with the EOSC-Core and between the components.

DELIVERY SLIP

Contribution	Name	Partner/Activity	ORCID
Lead author(s)	Mark van de Sanden	SURF	0000-0002-2718-8918
Contributor(s)	Ramy-Badr Ahmed	LZI	
	Maxence Azzouz-Thuderoz	FIZ	0000-0002-8710-9548
	Sven Bingert	GWDG	0000-0001-9547-1582
	Serafeim Chatzopoulos	OPENAIRE	0000-0003-1714-5225
	Mike Bennet	DataCite	
	Giacomo Cannizzaro	SURF	0000-0003-3623-4987
	Morane Gruenpeter	INRIA	0000-0002-9777-5560
	Wim Hugo	DANS	0000-0002-0255-5101
	Joonas Kesäniemi	CSC	0000-0002-3770-0006
	Hans Lienhop	GWDG	0000-0002-0066-4953
	Lars Holm Nielsen	CERN	0000-0001-8135-3489
	Maud Medves	INRIA	0000-0002-0624-1564
	Alain Monteil	INRIA	0000-0003-3150-4837
	Rumana Quazi	CSC	
	Shawn Ross	ARDC	0000-0002-6492-9025
	Kyle Snyder	SURF	0000-0001-8416-2442
	Wilko Steinhoff	DANS	0000-0003-1106-8441
	Tommi Suominen	CSC	0000-0002-4382-7425
	Clifford Tatum	SURF	0000-0002-2212-3197
	Thanasis Vergoulis	OpenAIRE	0000-0003-0555-4128
	Sarala Wimalaratne	DataCite	0000-0002-5355-2576
Reviewer(s)	Daan Broeder	CLARIN	0000-0002-8446-3410
	Roksana Wilk	CYFRONET	0009-0006-5321-1006

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
AARC	Authentication and Authorisation for Research Collaborations
API	Application Programming Interface
ARGO	ARGO is a lightweight service for Service Level Monitoring designed for medium and large sized Research Infrastructures
ARK	Archival Resource Key
ATOM	Atom Syndication Format is an XML language used for web feeds
arXiv	arXiv is a free distribution service and an open-access archive for scholarly articles
BibTeX/BibLaTeX	BibTeX is reference management software for formatting lists of references
B2FIND	EUDAT interdisciplinary discovery portal for research output
B2INST	EUDAT service for registering PIDs for Instruments
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics, the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance
CAT	EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit component
CC	Creative Commons license
CERN	Organisation Europeenne Pour La Recherche Nuclear
CFF	Common File Format
CLIMATE	FAIRCORE4EOSC Climate Change case study
CNRI	Corporation for National Research Initiatives
CMIP6	In climatology, the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) is a collaborative framework designed to improve knowledge of climate change. CMIP6 indicates phase 6.
Codemeta	Minimal metadata schemas for science software and code
CRIS	Current Research Information System
Crossref	Crossref is a non-profit open digital infrastructure organisation for the global scholarly research community
CRUD	Create, Read, Update and Delete operations
CSV	Comma Separated Values text file format
CSL	Citation Style Language
C4Model	C4 model is a lean graphical notation technique for modelling the architecture of software systems
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
DataCite	DataCite is an international not-for-profit organization which aims to improve data citation
Dataverse	Dataverse is an open-source web application to share, preserve, cite, explore and analyse research data.
DEMO	FAIRCORE4EOSC Demonstrators
DIF	Directory Interchange Format standard
DKRZ	Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GMBH
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DOIP	Digital Object Interface Protocol
DTR	EOSC Data Type Registry
eduGAIN	eduGAIN is an international interederation service interconnecting research and education identity federations.
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-Core	The components of EOSC that together deliver the essential operations of EOSC, including resource onboarding, discovery, ordering, use, monitoring, accounting and support, including the federated delivery of consistent services across a distributed "system of systems".
EOSC-Exchange	The collection of resources and organisations onboarded to the EOSC-Core, visible in the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace, and findable accessible and usable by EOSC Users.
EPIC	ePIC consortium of European partners in order to provide PID services for the European Research Community, based on the handle system
EUDAT	EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable and Reusable, FAIR Principles
FIZ	FIZ Karlsruhe - Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur GMBH
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIT	Git is a distributed version control system
GitHub	Platform that allows developers to create, store, and manage their software code
GraphQL	Graph Query Language
GRNET	Greek National Infrastructures for Research and Technology
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GWDG	Gesellschaft Für Wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung MBH Göttingen
HLR	High-Level Roadmap
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
INRIA	Institut National de Recherche en Informatique et Automatique
InvenioRDM	Invenio is an open-source software framework for large-scale digital repositories
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO19115	Geographic information Metadata
JIRA	Software for agile project management and to track issues
JS	JavaScript
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation Linked Data format
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LaTeX	LaTeX is markup language describing the content and layout of the document
LZI	Schloss Dagstuhl - Leibniz Zentrum für Informatik GMBH
MATH	FAIRCORE4EOSC Mathematics case study
MIME	Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions
MSCR	EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry
MS	Milestone
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
NATIONAL-SERVICE	FAIRCORE4EOSC European Integration of National-level Services case study
NL	Natural Language
NREN	National Research and Education Network
N/A	Not Applicable
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenAIRE	OPENAIRE AMKE
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier
OSG	Open Science Graph
PDF	Portable Data Format
PID	Persistent Identifier
PIDGraph	EOSC Persistent Identifier Graph
PIDMR	EOSC Persistent Identifier Meta Resolver
POSI	The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure
Quarkus	Quarkus is a Java framework tailored for deployment on Kubernetes
RAID	EOSC Research Activity Identifier
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDGraph	EOSC Research Discovery Graph
REST	Representational State Transfer application programming interface
RI	Research Infrastructure
ROR	Research Organisation Registry Identifier
RSAC	EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors
SCM	Synthetic Control Method
SERVICES-AND-RDM	FAIRCORE4EOSC EOSC Service Providers & RDM Communities case study

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SIRS	Scholarly Infrastructures of Research Software report
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graphs
SKG IF	Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMS	Service Management System
SPECS	Specifications
SQL	Structured Query Language
SRIA	EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSH	FAIRCORE4EOSC Social Sciences and Humanities case study
SSO	Single Sign On
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings
Swagger	Swagger is a suite of tools for API developers
SW	Software
SWH	Software Heritage
SWHID	Software Heritage intrinsic identifiers
SWHM	EOSC Software Heritage Mirror
swMATH	zbMATH Open (formerly known as Zentralblatt MATH) is the world's most comprehensive and longest-running abstracting and reviewing service in pure and applied mathematics.
Sword	Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit is an interoperability standard that allows digital repositories to accept the deposit of content from multiple sources
TBA	To Be Announced
TBD	To Be Defined
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology, the TRUST Principles
UI	User Interface
URN:NBN	Uniform Resource Name: National Bibliography Number
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UX	User Experience
WIP	Work In Progress
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XSLT	Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformations
XSD	W3C XML Schema Definition Language
Zenodo	Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN

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Executive Summary

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), one of the pillars for the realisation of the European Strategy for Data, is an ecosystem of research data and related services that will enable and enhance seamless access to and reliable re-use of FAIR research outputs (including data, publications, software, etc.). One of the priorities highlighted in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) is the establishment of the Web of FAIR data and a Minimum Viable EOSC by 2027, featuring the core components and functions to enable EOSC to operate. The development of the EOSC-Core was initiated in the Horizon 2020 calls which have delivered a rich palette of use cases, demonstrations, data, services and tools. However, there are still challenges that require to be addressed.

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project started in June 2022 and will deliver nine new EOSC-Core components in support of a FAIR research life cycle, bridging the gaps identified in the EOSC SRIA. More specifically, the components will enable an EOSC PID infrastructure, an EOSC research software infrastructure, support for sharing and access to metadata schemas and crosswalks and offer advanced research-intent driven discovery services over all EOSC repositories.

This deliverable summarises the technical status of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components and the functionalities available in the Beta Release (M18). The report is based on the input received by WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 via the milestones at M16. At M18 four components reached TRL7 and three at TRL6. The TRL levels of the sub-components of the Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC) component are not averaged to a single TRL level because the RSAC is not one component but are six independent developments for 6 independent services (2 scholarly repositories, 2 publishers and 2 aggregators). Next to an overview of the technical status of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components it also provides an overview of the project high-level roadmap and the status of requirements gathering process.

Finally, the report also includes a chapter describing the development activities planned between M18-M34, including the activities planned in terms of integration with the EOSC-Core and between the components.

1 Introduction

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), one of the pillars for the realisation of the European Strategy for Data, is an ecosystem of research data and related services that will enable and enhance seamless access to and reliable re- use of FAIR research outputs (including data, publications, software, etc.). One of the priorities highlighted in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) is the establishment of the Web of FAIR data and a Minimum Viable EOSC by 2027, featuring the core components and functions to enable EOSC to operate. The development of the EOSC-Core was initiated in the Horizon 2020 calls which have delivered a rich palette of use cases, demonstrations, data, services and tools. However, there are still challenges that require to be addressed.

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project started in June 2022 and will deliver nine new EOSC-Core components in support of a FAIR research life cycle, bridging the gaps identified in the EOSC SRIA. More specifically, the components will enable an EOSC PID infrastructure, an EOSC research software infrastructure, support for sharing and access to metadata schemas and crosswalks and offer advanced research-intent driven discovery services over all EOSC repositories.

After completing the initial specifications, described in deliverable D1.2¹, the implementation work has commenced with a milestone at M18 marking the BETA release of the components. This deliverable is a report summarising the technical status of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components and the functionalities available in the Beta Release. The report will also include a chapter describing the development activities planned between M18 and M34, including the activities planned in terms of integration.

1.1 FAIRCORE4EOSC implementation Methodology

The development of the new FAIRCORE4EOSC components revolves around four main implementation phases as depicted in the following Figure. All components to be developed will share this joint development timeline.

Phase 1: Collection of requirements and technical specifications

Phase 2: BETA release

Phase 3: Cross-integration BETA release

Phase 4: Production release and final documentation

¹ Suominen, T., Atzori, C., Baglioni, M., Tsapelas, C., Katsogiannis, G., Chatzopoulos, S., Vergoulis, T., Eleftherakis, S., Manghi, P., Iatropoulou, K., Galouni, K., Wimalaratne, S., Kesäniemi, J., Broeder, D., Bingert, S., Ariyo, C., Lienhop, H., Tolley, S., Leney, R., ... Kauranen, P. (2023). D1.2 FAIRCORE4EOSC Technical Specifications (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892322>

Figure 1 FAIRCORE4EOSC implementation Methodology

At the time of the submission deadline of this deliverable (M18) the project is at phase 2, the Beta Release.

1.2 Requirement analysis

During the initial requirements collection process a total of more than 500 requirements has been collected. To manage the process of requirements structuring, accepting and/or rejecting a JIRA agile board has been configured in which all the requirements have been registered.

Table 1 provides a cross matrix overview of the requirements between the Case Studies, Demonstrators and the FAIRCORE4EOSC components. From a case study (i.e. CLIMATE, SSH, MATH, NATIONAL-SERVICE, SERVICES-AND-RDM) perspective the table indicates which case study has defined requirements for which component. The table is also showing the number of requirements coming forth from the demonstrators (i.e. DEMO). The final column (T) shows the total unique requirements defined by the case studies or demonstrators or for the individual FAIRCORE4EOSC components. At time of this report, there are a total of 175 requirements (JIRA issues) registered related to the case-studies and a 107 which are cross-component. The other requirements are component specific.

Table 1 Requirements case study, demonstrator and component cross matrix

Components/ Case Studies	Components/Case Studies														
	CAT	CLIMATE	DEMO	DTR	MATH	MSCR	NATIONAL-SERVICE	PID Graph	PIDMR	RAiD	RD Graph	RSAC	SERVICES-AND-RDM	SSH	T
CAT	34	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34
CLIMATE	0	44	0	13	0	12	0	9	0	10	8	0	0	0	44
DEMO	0	0	62	18	0	34	0	9	0	0	14	0	0	0	62
DTR	0	13	18	49	2	13	0	3	0	1	0	0	4	5	49
MATH	0	0	0	2	16	2	0	6	2	2	0	1	0	0	16
MSCR	0	12	34	13	2	69	11	1	0	0	0	0	4	6	69
NATIONAL-SERVICE	0	0	0	0	0	11	24	3	0	7	1	2	0	0	24

Components/ Case Studies	Components/Case Studies														
	CAT	CLIMATE	DEMO	DTR	MATH	MSCR	NATIONAL -SERVICE	PID Graph	PIDMR	RAiD	RD Graph	RSAC	SERVICES -AND-RDM	SSH	T
PIDGraph	0	9	9	3	6	1	3	46	0	2	7	0	0	3	46
PIDMR	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	70	0	0	0	0	5	70
RAiD	0	10	0	1	2	0	7	2	0	204	4	0	1	0	204
RDGraph	0	8	14	0	0	0	1	7	0	4	52	0	0	1	52
RSAC	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	35
SERVICES- AND-RDM	0	0	0	4	0	4	0	0	0	1	0	0	10	0	10
SSH	0	0	0	5	0	6	0	3	5	0	1	0	0	19	19
Total Unique Issues:	34	44	62	49	16	69	24	46	70	204	52	35	10	19	534

Tables 2, 3 and 4 provide an overview on the status of the requirements:

- Table 2: Overview from the case study and demonstrator perspective
- Table 3: Overview from the FAIRCORE4EOSC perspective
- Table 4: Status overview from unique requirements perspective

The columns in tables 2, 3 and 4 have the following definitions:

- New: Requirements which have not yet been processed or analysed by the development teams
- Requirement Restructuring: Requirements which are currently being processed, analysed and refined by the development teams
- Accepted: Requirements which have been processed and selected for development (an in-scope requirement for the component) or done
- Done: Subset of the accepted requirements which have been applied by the development teams
- Out-of-Scope: Requirements which have been analysed and rejected because they are out of scope of the component in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project
- Total: Total count of requirements per each case study, demonstrators or component

Table 2 Case study requirements status

Case studies and Demonstrators	New	Requirement Restructuring	Accepted	Done*	Out-of-Scope	Total
CLIMATE	15	13	14	0	2	44
SSH	9	5	3	1	2	19
MATH	8	4	4	0	0	16
NATIONAL-SERVICE	14	1	9	0	0	24
SERVICES-AND-RDM	5	4	1	1	0	10

Case studies and Demonstrators	New	Requirement Restructuring	Accepted	Done*	Out-of-Scope	Total
DEMO	28	8	26	8	0	62
Total	79	35	57	10	4	175

* The number of requirements listed in the column Done are not included in the totals because the column Done is a subset of the Accepted column

Table 3 Component requirements status

Components	New	Requirement Restructuring	Accepted	Done*	Out-of-Scope	Total
CAT	19	4	11	9	0	34
RDGraph	33	6	12	7	1	52
PIDGraph	27	6	8	5	0	41
MSCR	37	10	21	0	1	69
DTR	22	17	9	2	1	49
RAiD	49	76	76	1	3	204
PIDMR	6	11	51	18	2	70
RSAC	13	12	10	4	0	35
Total	206	142	198	46	8	554

* The number of requirements listed in the column Done are not included in the totals because the column Done is a subset of the Accepted column

Table 4 Unique requirements status

Requirements	New	Requirement Restructuring	Accepted	Done	Out-of-Scope ²	Total
Total Unique Issues:	202	136	188	41	8	534

1.3 Technology Readiness Levels

To measure the maturity, the maturity of the components is based on the Technology Readiness Levels concept as defined by the EC³. Because the EC TRL levels are defined in very general terms and are not a natural fit for software and/or for service developments, the project related the TRL levels to software releases and to the service development lifecycle of services, see table 5.

² 2 requirements are considered not capability of a component, 2 requirements are implemented in an alternative way, and 4 requirements are considered out-of-scope of the project developments.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

Table 5 Mapping software releases and service development lifecycle to TRL levels

Software	Service	TRL
Pre-alpha		1-3
Alpha	Proof-of-Concept	4-5
Beta	Pilot	6
Release candidate	Beta	7
Release	Production	8
Release	Service running production for >1	9

1.3 High-level Roadmap

The purpose of the High-level Roadmap is to show and manage the evolution of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components in time. Table 6 shows the evolution of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components and component capabilities in time.

Table 6 High-level Roadmap components

FC4E Component	Service Components	M12	M18 (Beta-Release)	M22 (Cross-Integration Beta-Release)	M26	M30	M34
CAT	Compliance Vocabulary API		TRL3	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
	Compliance Assessment API	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
	Administration and Maintenance API	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
	Compliance Status Query API	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8
	Compliance Toolkit UI	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8
RDGraph	Graph data service	TRL3	TRL7	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8
	Natural language search	TRL4	TRL5	TRL5	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7
	Impact-based search	TRL3	TRL7	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Community recommendation profiles	TRL3	TRL4	TRL4	TRL5	TRL5	TRL6
	RAiD inference service		TRL2	TRL4	TRL5	TRL5	TRL6
	RDGraph portals	TRL5	TRL7	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
PIDGraph	PID Graph harvesting service	TRL3	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	PID link claims service	TRL5	TRL5	TRL5	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8
	Data Usage Statistics service via the EOSC-Core	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
MSCR	Content Registry	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8

FC4E Component	Service Components	M12	M18 (Beta-Release)	M22 (Cross-Integration Beta-Release)	M26	M30	M34
	Crosswalk Editor	TRL3	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Authorization and Authentication	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
DTR	Data Type Registry	TRL7	TRL7				
	DTR Toolkit	TRL4	TRL5				
RAiD	RAiD Registration Agency Service	TRL5	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	raid.org global search and resolution service		TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8
PIDMR	Meta Resolver Core	TRL4	TR 5	TRL6	TRL7		
	PID Meta Resolver UI	TRL4	TRL5	TRL6	TRL7		
	PID Meta Resolver API	TRL4	TRL6				
RSAC	Dagstuhl - SWH		TRL5	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9
	Dataverse - SWH	TRL4	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Episciences - SWH		TRL4				
	InvenioRDM - SWH	TRL4	TRL6	TRL8	TRL9	TRL9	TRL9
	OpenAire - SWH		TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	SwMath - SWH	TRL4	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8	TRL9
SWHM	Script to archive EOSC Core Components	TRL4	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8	TRL9
	SWH Mirror		TRL4	TRL5	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9

1.4 Beta Release

To measure the maturity of the newly developed components (KPI 3) the project used the concept of the Minimum Viable Product (MVP). On Wikipedia the MVP⁴ is defined as following:

*A **minimum viable product (MVP)** is a version of a product with just enough features to be usable by early customers who can then provide feedback for future product development.*

Table 7 describes KPI 3 *Maturity of newly developed components* as defined in the proposal.

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Minimum_viable_product

Table 7 Project definition of KPI 3

Measure	Baseline (M0)	Value (M18)	Value (M36)	Indicator of quality
KPI 3 - Maturity of newly developed components	8/0/0	8/6/0	8/1/7	Number of components (i.e. total planned/at TRL7/at TRL8)

For each of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components, the development teams defined the capabilities/functions of the service components to be included in the MVP, a more detailed description of the MVPs can be found in *sections 2 Minimum Viable Product* of the individual components. To assess the maturity level of the MVP, the maturity levels of the individual service components and capabilities/functions is averaged and rounded, not accounting the lowest and/or highest TRL level. Table 8 provides an overview of the TRLs of the component MVP's.

Table 8 High-level Roadmap components

FAIRCORE4EOSC component	Maturity Level MVP
EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)	TRL6
EOSC Research Discovery Graph (RDGRAPH)*	TRL6
EOSC PID Graph (PID Graph)*	TRL6
EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)	TRL7
EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR)*	TRL7
EOSC Research Activity Identifier service (RAID)	TRL7
EOSC PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR)	TRL7
EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC)*	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dagstuhl - SWH</i> 	TRL5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dataverse - SWH</i> 	TRL6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Episciences - SWH</i> 	TRL4
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>InvenioRDM - SWH</i> 	TRL6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>OpenAire - SWH</i> 	TRL6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>SwMath - SWH</i> 	TRL7

* Note: FAIRCORE4EOSC developments are extensions to mature existing services

From the table above, it can be concluded that the project did not fully meet KPI 3. At the M18 Beta-release milestone 4 components reached TRL7 and 3 reached TRL6. The TRL levels of the sub-components of the RSAC component are not averaged to a single TRL level because the RSAC is not one component but are six independent developments for 6 independent services (2 scholarly repositories, 2 publishers and 2 aggregators). More detailed information can be found in sections 2-9.

Appendix 1 provides an overview of references to beta-releases of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Components and sub-components made available at M18.

2 EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)

The Compliance Assessment Toolkit for EOSC: a set of concepts, implemented as a graph database and accessible via APIs, and supported by user interfaces via the APIs. The Compliance Assessment Toolkit will support the EOSC PID policy with services to encode, record, and query compliance with the policy. To do so, a wide range of compliance requirements (TRUST, FAIR, PID Policy, Reproducibility, GDPR, Licences) will be evaluated as use cases for definition of a conceptual model. At the same time, vocabularies, concepts, and designs are intended to be re-usable for other compliance needs: TRUST, FAIR, POSI, CARE, Data Commons, etc. This will be followed by a supporting service specification (the framework), accompanied by development and testing of operational services for PID Policy Compliance monitoring. Though primarily aimed at machine-actionable operations, the API-based services will be complemented by user interfaces to broaden its use.

2.1 CAT Minimum Viable Product

The beta version of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) is a deployed version with the basic features that are needed.

Table 9 High-Level Roadmap of Compliance Assessment Toolkit MVP

Capabilities/ Functions	Description	MVP	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
Create and edit/update vocabulary items	For a given vocabulary, add an element (label or term), or add/update relations between vocabulary elements. or register a new relation type. Can be shared with MSCR/ EOSC vocabulary service		-	TRL3	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
List/ retrieve vocabulary elements and details	List the available vocabularies, elements of a vocabulary, and the details of a specific vocabulary element. Can be shared with MSCR/ EOSC vocabulary service		-	TRL3	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
Add a vocabulary	Add a vocabulary to the list of vocabularies. Can be shared with MSCR/ EOSC vocabulary service		-	TRL3	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
Add, edit, and delete an assessment	An API for managing an assessment record to the CAT database	V	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
Add, manage, and define user roles	Add and manage, disable users and their responsibilities in the CAT API services	V	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8

Capabilities/ Functions	Description	MVP	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
Query the CAT database in respect of compliance status of actors	Actors include PID Scheme (Component), PID Authority (Role), PID Service Provider (Role), PID Service (Component), PID Manager (Role), PID Owner (Role), End User (Role), Compliance Monitoring (Role)		TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8
Administrator View	Add, edit, delete vocabularies Add, edit, delete, and administer users and SSO	V	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8
User Account View	Register a user, request user-validation, associate with roles	V	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8
Contributor View	Add, edit, and delete vocabulary elements	V	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8
General End User View	List, query, and explore vocabularies Explore compliance history and status of an actor, object, or service.		TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8
Evaluator/ Assessment System View	View past assessments performed Add a new assessment (by reference, by value)	V	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL6	TRL8	TRL8
Dashboard/ Discovery	Summary of compliance assessments and status across actors, objects, and services for each type of assessment regime Link to listings and individual status/history views		TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8

2.2 CAT requirements overview

Table 10 CAT requirements overview

User Story - Landscape Analysis	New	Restructuring	Accepted	Out-of-scope	Total
Users of persistent identifiers want to assess the level of compliance of foundational actors in the PID ecosystem to determine the most appropriate service to use in the context of the EOSC PID Policy. (Foundational actors - schemes, authorities, service providers, and managers).	0	0	8	3	11
Providers of persistent identifier services need to be able to substantiate and publish the level of compliance with EOSC PID Policy. Such publications are citable and versioned.	0	0	14	0	14
User Story - External engagement					
There is a general need expressed in international forums to disambiguate and align assessment of TRUST, and by extension those for FAIR. (The conceptual model and its vocabulary is designed to address this need). This project extends the	0	0	4	0	4

User Story - Landscape Analysis	New	Restructuring	Accepted	Out-of-scope	Total
approach proposed there to accommodate PID Policy compliance assessment.					
Institutional users of persistent identifiers want to obtain guidance on best practices and recommendations in terms of implementation. The guidance applies in two categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how to use or provide actionable persistent identifiers best, depending on the use case, • and how to develop policy in respect of identifiers. 	1	0	8	0	9

Table 11 Compliance Assessment Toolkit overview requirements MVP

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP2_T2_CAT_3.1 Manage User Roles	Placeholder user accounts for each defined role. Add, manage, and define user roles	CSCFC4EREQ-428
WP2_T2_CAT_3.2 Manage Identified User Roles	User registers as an 'Identified' user -role is assigned automatically, no further action required.	CSCFC4EREQ-429
WP2_T2_CAT_3.3 Manage Validated User Roles	User registers as a 'validated' user - admin needs to validate and assign a role. In order for a User to be assigned with this role, he should update his profile and make a validation request with the required fields	CSCFC4EREQ-430
WP2_T2_CAT_2.3 Add compliance assessments manually	Add compliance assessment manually for a PID owner	CSCFC4EREQ-426
WP2_T2_CAT_2.2 Add compliance assessments manually	Add compliance assessment manually for a PID Manager	CSCFC4EREQ-425
WP2_T2_CAT-5.2 Administrator Dashboard for users	Administrator opens a dashboard-like view of users, able to edit, add, and remove users.	CSCFC4EREQ-435
WP2_T2_CAT-5.3 Administrator Dashboard for pending requests	Administrator opens a dashboard-like view of users, and filters on pending validation requests. Administrator can confirm or reject validation,	CSCFC4EREQ-436
WP2_T2_CAT-6.1 Add, edit, and delete registry information for the user	Add, edit, and delete registry information for the user - provide a dashboard-like view that corresponds to the first page of a manual assessment to confirm, edit, and delete information about a specific service or object. Display an assessment history for an object.	CSCFC4EREQ-437
WP2_T2_CAT-6.2 A validated user requests or registers a new manual external assessment.	A validated user requests or registers a new manual external assessment. This assessment has the following steps and sub-components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide or confirm information about the submitter (=logged-in user account) • Select the type of assessment (Scheme, Authority, Provider, Manager, ...) • Define whether the assessment should be private, or whether it is licenced under CC 4.0 BY. • Provide information about the assessment target, and a pointer to a validated assessment result. The assessment result needs to conform to the assessment exchange specification. 	CSCFC4EREQ-438
WP2_T2_CAT-6.3 A validated user requests or registers a new manual assessment.	A validated user requests or registers a new manual assessment. This assessment has the following steps and sub-components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide or confirm information about the submitter (=logged-in user account) 	CSCFC4EREQ-439

Requirement	Short description	Reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Select the type of assessment (Scheme, Authority, Provider, Manager, ...) Define whether the assessment should be private, or whether it is licenced under CC 4.0 BY. Provide information about the assessment target by filling in the evaluation form. <p>Support is provided by making benchmarking, guidelines, and best practices information available.</p>	

2.3 CAT Overview and the status of the development

2.3.1 CAT API

The Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT): CAT API^{5,6}, is built on the Quarkus framework, providing a secure and efficient solution for client validation and assessment management. Through designated API endpoints, clients can validate themselves, enabling access to features like assessment creation and management, as well as the customization of profile information, including name, surname, email, and ORCID ID.

To ensure the security of all interactions, our API is protected by the AAI Proxy, safeguarding each endpoint. Clients can obtain specific roles that determine their access permissions, defining which endpoints they can interact with. The entire authorization process is handled through Keycloak, ensuring a robust and reliable authentication mechanism for a smooth user experience.

CAT API also empowers administrators with efficient and dynamic user management capabilities, allowing them to control the validation process and roles. Administrators can navigate through Users validation requests, approving or rejecting them as needed whilst at the same time they have the authority to assign specific roles to different users, defining access permissions based on organizational needs.

The main functionalities the API currently supports (based on the permissions a user has)

- Validation Requests: The management of the validation requests
- Assessments: The management of the manual assessment
- Integrations: The API supports the integration with external systems. The first integration refers to ROR and it is used when a user is creating a validation request for a specific actor
- Other: Code lists, Filters, and endpoints that help the client use the API

2.3.2 CAT UI

The Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT): CAT UI⁷ is a web-application, created using the React JavaScript framework. It also uses JS Typescript as a technology for a “clean” code, and of-course for making the code more scalable. The main goal of the CAT-UI is to assist actors in the PID ecosystem with assessment of their compliance with the EOSC PID policy. The CAT-UI supports different levels of authorization for registered users, separating the UI capabilities for administrators and simple users. Key features like user authentication using EOSC-AAI demo instances (through the use of Keycloak⁸), automatic user registration, and basic user profile configurations are supported.

⁵ <https://api.cat.argo.grnet.gr/swagger-ui/#/> (API definition)

⁶ <https://api.cat.argo.grnet.gr/> (API service endpoint)

⁷ <https://cat.argo.grnet.gr/>

⁸ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

The CAT-UI follows a list of design patterns, tips and best practices for the flow of information in order to solve common problems in user interface design. This leads to a dashboard-like UI with interfaces that are both consistent and efficient. The UI supports:

- Consistent tables, with pagination, and sorting features
- Filters in specific views that help the user find what they want quickly, saving time and reducing frustration
- Consistent notification messages for the interaction with the API
- Autocompletion on input forms and more refined UI layouts
- Wizard-like forms
- Tooltips, help messages, and information are key features of the UI
- TypeScript declarations and updated assessment schemas are also used

The UI consists of the following main views:

- Assessments per actor: This is a public view where visitors can be informed about the latest assessments made by the different actor types
- User Validations: A user can manage as many requests for becoming an actor as he wants.
- User Profile: The place where the user can manage its validations, assessments and profile data.
- Management of assessments: The validated user can easily manage its own assessments for the different actors. He can create, update, delete, search or even export the assessment he/she wants. For the creation of new assessments, the UI supports a wizard step by step component. The wizard guides the dashboard user through-out the necessary steps for creating a valid assessment request. An algorithm that follows the conceptual model and the combination of principles, criteria, and metrics is also part of the UI. In the latest version of the UI dynamic features that allow the display of principles, criteria, and metrics for the assessment creation view are key to the user support.

The deployed beta version of the CAT-UI implements the basic features to validate the conceptual model, principles and metrics. Next to provide feedback on the basic features, the early end-users can also provide feedback on future developments to advance the UI assessment process and the user experience.

3 EOSC Research Discovery Graph Service (RDGraph)

The EOSC Research Discovery Graph Service (RDGraph) aims at delivering advanced discovery tools across EOSC resources and communities. The RDGraph extends the content of the EOSC catalogue with additional entities like the Research Activity Identifiers (RAiDs), while offering functionality similar to several community-oriented discovery tools. The RDGraph service provides a set of tools that exploit natural language processing and graph-based solutions for EOSC users to explore research entities (publications, data, software). The RDGraph will be made accessible via intuitive UI/UX portals, regular data dumps and APIs to support data re-use and third-party service interoperability. The RDGraph Service comprises several sub-components, each supporting different functionalities; the following table lists some useful resources about them, i.e., links to code repositories, documentation, and demonstration websites.

Table 12 Information related to the RDGraph sub-components

Sub-component	Code repo	Documentation	Beta demo
Graph data service	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/bioentities-preprocess https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dhp-graph-dump	https://graph.openaire.eu	N/A
Natural language search	https://github.com/athenarc/fc4eosc-nlsearch	https://test.darelab.athenarc.gr/text-to-sql/docs	https://test.darelab.athenarc.gr/text-to-sql/fc4eosc
Impact-based search	https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/graph-production-workflow/indicators-ingestion/impact-indicators	https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu
Community recommendation profiles	https://github.com/athenarc/fc4eosc-recommender	https://test.darelab.athenarc.gr/crps-rec/docs https://test.darelab.athenarc.gr/crps-rec/redoc	http://test.darelab.athenarc.gr/crps/
RAiD inference service	TBD, not part of beta MVP	TBD, not part of beta MVP	TBD, not part of beta MVP
RDGraph portals	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/faircore4eosc-explore	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/faircore4eosc-explore/src/branch/main/README.md	https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu

3.1 RDGraph Minimum Viable Product

In the context of the Beta release, the Beta version of the RDGraph MVP will include, for each sub-component, the capabilities/functions presented in the following table. Specifically, the table also contains the maturity level (TRL) of each sub-component capability/function in different time points of the project lifetime.

Table 13 High-Level Roadmap of RDGraph MVP

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
Graph data service	RDGraph data provision workflow	This component is responsible to perform the required workflows to generate the RDGraph from the EOSC resource catalogue content, as well as offer these data via appropriate APIs and regular data dumps.	TRL5	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	RDGraph dumps		TRL3	TRL3	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8
	RDGraph APIs		TRL3	TRL3	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8
Natural language search	Empower the user to search and perform queries on the RDGraph using Natural Language	A system based on neural networks that can translate the user's NL Query into a Query Language that can be executed over the RDGraph, so that the user can seamlessly search the graph without the need of technical expertise.	TRL4	TRL5	TRL5	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7
Impact-based search	Rank research products according to impact-based indicators	Enables discovery of products and services by exploiting impact-based indicators (i.e., citation count, popularity, influence) in the ranking and filtering mechanisms of the search functionality.	TRL4	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Filter research products based on impact-based indicators		TRL4	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
Community recommendations on profiles	Recommend a personalized list of research products per community user.	Community profiles can capture user preferences and improve the user's experience by using recommendation algorithms that mine feedback from the community's users.	TRL3	TRL4	TRL4	TRL5	TRL5	TRL6
RDGraph portals	Discovery portal	Enables discovery, monitoring and access to research products and services in the RDGraph.	TRL5	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8

3.2 RDGraph requirements overview

RDGraph aims at facilitating scientific discovery focusing on EOSC-related content. In this context, various requirements for the component are related to persistent identifiers (PIDs). PIDs have been identified in EOSC SRIA as an important concept. They have also been recognised within the FAIR principles as a key feature supporting the findability and accessibility of research objects. RDGraph is using PIDs of various types in its metadata forming a rich resource to search and contextualise research products. In addition, some important RDGraph requirements are related to the wider need for interoperability (again identified in EOSC SRIA) since the component will focus on the interoperability framework for graph data exchange.

Table 14 RDGraph requirements overview

Case study	New	Restructuring	Accepted	Out-of-scope	Total
Climate Change	6	0	2	0	8
Social Sciences and Humanities	1	0	0	0	1
Mathematics	0	0	0	0	0
European integration of National-level Services	1	0	0	0	1
EOSC Service Providers & RDM Communities	0	0	0	0	0
Demonstrators					
B2FIND integration in RDGraph and PIDGraph	0	2	4	0	6
Integration of Graph information in B2FIND to avail and utilise Graph in the discovery portal	4	0	0	0	4
OSG Graph info extends B2FIND Metadata Schema	1	0	0	0	1
Component					
Graph data service	2	0	0	0	2
Impact based search	0	3	1	0	4
Supporting natural language search	3	0	0	0	3
Community recommendation profiles	2	0	0	0	2
RAiD inference	1	0	1	0	2
RDGraph Portals	10	0	0	0	10

Table 15 RDGraph overview requirements MVP

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP3.T3.2_RDGRAPH dump support of guidelines for SKG IF ⁹	RDGraph dumps facilitate interoperability following the guidelines of SKG IF	CSCFC4EREQ-539
WP3.T3.2_RDGRAPH APIs support of guidelines for SKG IF	RDGraph APIs facilitate interoperability following the guidelines of SKG IF	CSCFC4EREQ-540
WP3.T3.3_RDGRAPH capture user's intent in translated SQL query	Generate SQL queries from natural language queries effectively capturing user's intent	CSCFC4EREQ-27
WP3.T3.3_RDGraph - sort search results with impact indicators	Support ranking of search results using impact indicators	CSCFC4EREQ-18
WP3.T3.3_RDGraph - recommendations based on the user id or the research product id	Community members should be able to get recommendations based on the user id or the research product id.	CSCFC4EREQ-23
WP3.T3.4_RDGraph - search results based on keywords	Users should be able to discover the content of RDGraph using keyword-based search	CSCFC4EREQ-520
WP3.T3.4_RDGraph - filter results based on metadata	Users should be able to filter the results of keyword-based search using filters on research products' metadata	CSCFC4EREQ-521

⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/scientific-knowledge-graphs-interoperability-framework-skg-if-wg>

3.3 RDGraph overview and the status of the developments

The following table summarises the development status of all RDGraph sub-components.

Table 16 Overview and status of RDGraph sub-components

Graph data service	
Work done	To support the activities in T3.3 we developed (i) a mapping from the internal RDGraph model towards a representation of the data suitable for the components implementing the NL Search and the Community Recommendation profiles, and (ii) a workflow for the automation of the process implementing such a mapping. Furthermore, we worked on the operation of the workflows for the scheduled generation of the RDGraph for the EOSC resource catalogue (metadata collection, validation, indexing). Work has been done for enhancing the APIs with impact based ranking and filtering of research products.
Next steps	The next step will include the creation of a conceptual mapping to represent the RDGraph contents according to the RDA SKG WG ¹⁰ specifications, to be used on the materialisation of the RDGraph through public APIs and publicly available datasets deposited on Zenodo. Following that conceptual mapping, the code to create the datasets and the response format via the API will be provided together with dedicated workflows for the scheduled generation of the datasets.
Issues & deviations	None
Natural language search	
Work done	We set up a relational database containing data from academic communities that were extracted from the OpenAIRE Graph / RDGraph. We created a service that uses a neural pre-trained language model to translate user questions from natural language (NL) to a SQL query. Our service can then execute the predicted SQL query on the relational database and return the data to the user. We also created a demo interface to showcase these capabilities.
Next steps	As next steps, we plan to showcase the use of our service in the context of the project's case-studies, as well as to improve the quality of the predicted SQL queries.
Issues & deviations	None
Impact-based search	
Work done	A dedicated workflow was implemented in the RDGraph provision process to calculate a set of impact indicators that are used for impact-based search. Specifically, citation relations between research products were extracted from the graph; these relations were used to construct the citation network which was then used to calculate the provided impact indicators. In particular, four impact indicators are calculated, including simple, yet widely established, citation counts as well as more sophisticated graph analysis techniques that can estimate the current (popularity), overall impact (influence), and initial impact (impulse) of research products. These impact indicators are then properly indexed to enable (a) impact-based ranking of research products (via the RDGraph portals), and (b) impact-based filtering of research products (via RDGraph APIs).
Next steps	As next steps, we aim at finalising the integration of functionalities to the RDGraph portals and showcase their use in the context of the FAIRCORE4EOSC case studies. Last but not least, we plan to investigate the integration of additional types of impact indicators.
Issues & deviations	None

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/scientific-knowledge-graphs-interoperability-framework-skg-if-wg>

Community recommendation profiles	
Work done	We extracted interactions between authors and research outputs across four specialised academic communities: mathematics, humanities, climate change, and data management. The dataset for the mathematics community was externally sourced from zbMATH, while the datasets for the remaining communities were extracted from the OpenAIRE Graph / RDGraph. Interactions were either authorship or citation, representing instances where a community user had either written or cited a particular research work. To authenticate users within these communities, the zbMATH author ID was employed for the mathematics community, and ORCID identifiers were used for the other communities. Based on this authenticated interaction data, we constructed a collaborative filtering-based recommender system. This system not only offers personalised recommendations of research works to users but is also capable of identifying similar publications given a publication of interest, thus serving a dual purpose: facilitating the targeted dissemination of academic articles and aiding users in discovering related research works for further reading.
Next steps	In subsequent phases of this project, we intend to enhance the recommender system's performance by leveraging side information related to the research works (e.g., keywords, titles, etc.). This additional data aims to refine the quality of the recommendations generated. Furthermore, we will address specific recommendation challenges, including fairness and diversity, tailored to the unique requirements of each academic community. These advancements are envisioned to optimise the utility and effectiveness of the recommender system, thereby better serving the academic communities in focus.
Issues & deviations	None
RAiD inference service	
Work done	Service design has started. Focus on the design of appropriate methodologies.
Next steps	We will implement graph-based approaches that will recommend possible entities in the graph that will constitute a new RAiD. In addition, we will consider entities in existing RAiDs to propose suggestions for their expansion (i.e., possible research products that can extend an existing RAiD).
Issues & deviations	Service implementation is dependent on the development of the EOSC RAiD service & the required changes in the RDGraph model.
RDGraph portals	
Work done	We have gathered basic requirements for the look and feel of the RDgraph search and discovery portal and we have participated in discussions on how the impact indicators are going to be integrated in the sorting functionality of research products. We have set up the initial version of the RDgraph search and discovery portal, currently running on local machines.
Next steps	We will deploy the version of the RDGraph search and discovery Portal with the integrated impact-based sorting functionality.
Issues & deviations	None.

4 EOSC PID Graph Service (PIDGraph)

The EOSC PID Graph Service (PIDGraph) is designed to provide services for the continuous population of and access provision to a PID Graph, which consists in the aggregation of records and links provided by PID authority data sources, such as ORCID, ROR, DataCite, and Crossref, and other trusted services. The PIDGraph will be available via regular data dumps comprising metadata for DOIs and links between PIDs in the graph, as well as via APIs supporting third party integration via common protocols (e.g. GraphQL, OAI-PMH, OpenAPI REST), and the provisioning of a Data Usage Statistics Service allowing integration of COUNTER-compliant statistics into the graph.

Table 17 Information related to the PID Graph sub-components

Sub-component	Code repo	Documentation	Beta demo
PID Graph harvesting service	https://github.com/datacite/ipo	TBA	https://api.datacite.org/graphql
PID Graph link claims service	https://github.com/datacite/evriero	TBA	N/A
Data usage statistics service via the EOSC Core	https://github.com/datacite/datacite-tracker/	https://support.datacite.org/docs/datacite-usage-tracker	N/A

4.1 PIDGraph Minimum Viable Product

The MVP for the EOSC PIDGraph service will consist of the provision of data dumps comprising DOI metadata and PID link claims along with a REST API allowing access to those data dumps, provision of PIDGraph data via standard APIs, and the initial release of the Data Usage Statistics service.

Table 18 High-Level Roadmap of PIDGraph MVP

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
PID Graph harvesting service	PIDGraph Dumps	This component provides access to the PIDGraph data via data dumps and APIs.	TRL3	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	PIDGraph APIs		TRL6	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
PID Graph link claims service	PID Link ingestion	This component will ingest additional links between PIDs and expose them in the PIDGraph	TRL5	TRL5	TRL5	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8
Data usage statistics service via the EOSC Core	Usage activity tracker	This component allows provision of Data Usage Statistics into the PIDGraph	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8

4.2 PIDGraph requirements overview

The main needs identified in EOSC SRIA that are addressed by the PID Graph component are related to persistent identifiers (PIDs). PIDs have been specifically recognised within the FAIR principles as a key feature supporting the findability and accessibility of research objects. PID Graph will facilitate the consumption of usage data from DataCite DOIs and integrated repositories, while it will also ingest (and expose) third-party links between PID entities. Finally, there are requirements related to the need for interoperability (again identified in EOSC SRIA) since the component will focus on the interoperability framework for graph data exchange.

Table 19 PID Graph requirements related to the SRIA

Requirement	Origin	Type
To be able to obtain a data dump up to last year	SRIA	accepted
To be able to obtain a data dump up to last month	SRIA	accepted
To be able to obtain a data dump in different formats	SRIA	accepted
To be able to harvest PID Graph data (nodes and edges) using standard protocol	SRIA	accepted
To be able to harvest resources affiliated to certain country	SRIA	accepted
To be able to harvest resources of a certain field of science	SRIA	accepted
To be able to provide same-as relationships assertions between document domain Identifiers and DOIs to the PID Graph	SRIA	accepted
To be able to provide same-as relationships assertions between author domain Identifiers and ORCID to the PID Graph	SRIA	accepted
To be able to provide part-of relationships assertions between document domain Identifiers and DOIs to the PID Graph	SRIA	accepted
To be able to provide usage data level metrics to the PID Graph	SRIA	accepted
To be able to request usage data level metrics from the PID Graph	SRIA	accepted

Table 20 PID Graph requirements overview

Case study	New	Restructuring	Accepted	Out-of-scope	Total
Climate Change	4	2	3	0	9
Social Sciences and Humanities	3	0	0	0	3
Mathematics	2	3	1	0	6
European integration of National-level Services	2	0	1	0	3
EOSC Service Providers & RDM Communities	0	0	0	0	0
Demonstrators					
Retrieve a sub graph and examine for B2FIND purposes	4	0	0	0	4
OSG Graph info extends B2FIND Metadata Schema	1	0	0	0	1

Table 21 PID Graph overview requirements MVP

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP3.T3.5_PID Graph metadata via data dumps	As a harvester, I would like to be able to have access to a data dump with all the DOI, ORCID, and ROR metadata records in so that I can bootstrap my metadata harvesting.	CSCFC4EREQ-2 CSCFC4EREQ-3 CSCFC4EREQ-4
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.57 CC: Query the PIDGraph	It should be possible to query the PIDGraph using a query language optimized for graph queries. The search can be performed using an API and a GUI.	CSCFC4EREQ-467
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.46 CC: Objects and links in PIDGraph	The PIDGraph contains papers (DOI), datasets (DOI and handle.net PIDs), projects (RAiD), ... These objects are linked together with links of different types to be able to understand the relationships & hierarchy between the different objects in the graph.	CSCFC4EREQ-455

WP3.T3.5_PID Graph query and harvesting by country	Query and harvest PIDGraph data filtered by country to enable National Level Service providers to bootstrap and enrich their own national systems.	CSCFC4EREQ-6 CSCFC4EREQ-7 CSCFC4EREQ-8
WP3.T3.5_PID Data Usage Statistics submission	As a provider of a data hosting platform, I would like to provide usage data level metrics to the PID graph about the resources identified with DOIs in my platform so that third parties can have access to them	CSCFC4EREQ-15
WP3.T3.5_PID Data Usage Statistics consumption	As a provider of a metadata indexing service and a discovery portal, I would like to be able to obtain usage data level metrics from scholarly outputs indexed in my service so as to enrich my metadata index and provide such metrics in my portal	CSCFC4EREQ-16

4.3 PIDGraph overview and the status of the developments

The following table summarizes the development status of all RDGraph sub-components.

Table 22 Overview and status of PIDGraph sub-components

PID Graph harvesting service	
Work done	The work on this component started with creation of the technical specification for the Data Dump service, followed by development work on the REST API for accessing the data dump files, and the start of development work for the creation and storage of the data dump files. Work also included improving the functionality of the underlying infrastructure and services that are the foundation for this component.
Next steps	Expansion of the Harvester service to meet remaining use cases, including filtering by country and domain of research.
Issues & deviations	None
PID Graph link claims service	
Work done	During this phase of the project, work was limited to improvements to the underlying infrastructure supporting the Event Data service that will underpin the PID Link Claims service.
Next steps	Development of agents for ingesting PID link claims from partners in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, along with publication of guidelines and specifications for providing the PID Link data.
Issues & deviations	None
Data usage statistics service via the EOSC Core	
Work done	Validation of the Usage Tracker service with a repository (Dryad)
Next steps	Resolve validation issues. Expose usage statistics collected via Usage Tracker in DataCite Commons
Issues & deviations	None

5 EOSC Metadata and Schema Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)

The MSCR is a registry service where users can store Metadata Schemas and Crosswalks. The MSCR allows registered users and communities to create, register and version schemas and crosswalks with PIDs. The published content can be searched, browsed and downloaded without restrictions. It provides communities, projects and individual researchers with the possibility to manage their metadata schema and/or relevant metadata schema crosswalks both via GUI and API and facilitate the transformation of data from one schema to another via registered crosswalks. The schema and crosswalks are shared with all for reuse and extensions are supported by a proper versioning mechanism.

5.1 MSCR Minimum Viable Product

As mentioned above, the MSCR is being developed with the focus of working as a registry of metadata schema and crosswalks which can be shared and used by the community. Keeping this in mind, the MSCR MVP was designed and implemented to have the content registration and management functionality as the initial feature. The MVP allows users to authenticate through EOSC AAI, upload the schema and crosswalk files which are registered in the MSCR with PIDs. With the registered schemas, users can also create simple crosswalks using a GUI. All the MVP features are also available through an API. The main MSCR sub components that are available in the MVP beta release are listed in the HLR table below.

Table 23 High-Level Roadmap of the MSCR MVP

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
Content Registry	Registration of Existing Schema and Crosswalks using an UI	The MSCR is a registry, every added piece of content is registered, hence registration refers to an act of adding a new schema/crosswalk record to the registry. Initially supported formats for Schemas are CSV, XSD and JSON Schema and XSLT for Crosswalks	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Version management of crosswalk and schemas	The content of schemas and crosswalks can be versioned and users can retrieve provenance information about any piece of content.	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Content search	Registered and hosted content is searchable and MSCR implements a separate search endpoint for faceted search which will support both text query and filtering based on facet values.	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
	Content Registration via API	MSCR will provide API Endpoints to register crosswalk and schemas.	TRL4	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
Crosswalk Editor	Support for simple structural mappings Support for value mappings	Crosswalk editor can be used to create structural mappings across all supported metadata schema formats. Mapping can include information needed for transformation of values as well (e.g from one enumeration to another or from one unit to another).	TRL3	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
Authorization and Authentication	MVP AAI integration User and group management Integrated group management for group admins API keys for User Management	MVP AAI integration allows users to login using the EOSC AAI. MSCR admins are able to assign roles and groups to registered users. Group admins are able to manage users and their roles within admin's own group. API tokens can be created for users and API tokens can be used as a sort of service account that can be configured for automated use of the MSCR API.	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8

5.2 MSCR requirements overview

Table 24 MSCR Requirements overview

Case study	New	Restructuring	Accepted	Out-of-scope	Total
Climate Change	4	4	3	1	12
Social Sciences and Humanities	4	1	1		6
Mathematics	2	0	0		2
European integration of National-level Services	8	1	2		11
EOSC Service Providers & RDM Communities	2	2			4
Demonstrators					
MSCR Managing B2FIND Schema and crosswalks	7	1	5	0	13
MSCR Managing B2SHARE schema	2	0	2	0	4
MSCR Seeding demonstrator to make FAIRer Semantic Artefacts	2	0	5	0	7

Table 24. MSCR overview requirements MVP

Requirement	Short description	Reference
US 4.5.2.1 MSCR Managing B2FIND Schemas and crosswalks	B2FIND manager registers B2FIND's community metadata schemas, EUDAT core schema and crosswalks between them	CSCFC4EREQ-50
UR 4.5.2.3.1 MSCR provides functionalities of the CW editor for B2FIND needs	MSCR provides Crosswalk Editor and guidelines on how to use it. As a smart mapping tool that allows creating crosswalks between metadata schema	CSCFC4EREQ-71
UR 4.5.6.1 MSCR Managing B2SHARE schema	MSCR registration and hosting of (community) metadata schema and performing basic administrative functions on these: metadating, versioning. (a metadata schema for MSCR semantic artefacts is tbd)	CSCFC4EREQ-75
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.34.MSCR CC: MSCR convert values between units	The MSCR is able to convert values into different units, e.g. convert degree Celsius to degrees Kelvin or degrees Fahrenheit.	CSCFC4EREQ-110
UR 4.5.1.1 MSCR seeding demonstrator	MSCR registration and hosting of semantic artefacts via API and GUI: metadata schema, metadata schema related vocabularies, schema crosswalks.	CSCFC4EREQ-55
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.33.MSCR CC: MSCR API and local usage	The MSCR must be accessible using an API to access vocabularies and their mappings. Furthermore, it should allow for conversion of vocabularies using the API as well as locally.	CSCFC4EREQ-109

5.3 MSCR overview and the status of the developments

5.3.1 MSCR Backend functionality

The Beta version of the MSCR supports registration of schemas in CSV (delimited list of column names), JSON Schema (Draft-04 specification), PDF and SKOS RDF formats. For the crosswalks, externally managed content can be registered in XSLT and PDF formats, and new crosswalks can be created from scratch using a tool in the MSCR's internal mapping format. The API provides a way to create and update schema and crosswalk related metadata and allows for searching all of the publicly available metadata as well as private workspace content visible only to the logged in user or an organisation associated with the user.

The beta release implements simple versioning of schemas and crosswalks by providing a way to aggregate multiple versions under a shared identifier. Each version has its own metadata instance with separate state and label information.

When a schema is registered in the MSCR, its original representation (e.g. JSON Schema file) is stored in the database and the content of the schema is transformed into a common internal schema format, which is SHACL. In the beta release, this transformation is implemented only for simple CSV schemas and JSON Schema draft-04. The planned support for additional JSON schema specifications and implementation of XSD import functionality will be a technical and domain knowledge challenge.

Support for registering SKOS vocabularies in other to support mapping between vocabularies (eg. [CSCFC4EREQ-108](#)) was a late addition, driven by the fact that multiple case studies require vocabulary mappings as part of their plans for crosswalk operationalization. As managing vocabularies is not part of the MSCR functionality, the need for a separate vocabulary service is under assessment.

The initial idea was to transform SKOS vocabularies to SHACL shapes similar to schemas, but that turned into overly complicated implementation. In the end, it was decided to treat vocabularies as a separate type of schema internally and do away with theoretically pleasing uniformity of internal schema representations in favour of specialised separate representation for schemas (e.g. JSON Schema) and vocabularies. *The next step related to vocabularies, will be a way to assign them as the allowed values of a schema property.*

We have developed our own internal model for storing mappings based on the requirements extracted from the existing crosswalks implemented by the case study organisations. These crosswalks are currently implemented for example as XSLT stylesheets and Python code. As part of the transformation engine development, we have implemented a first version of the transformation engine, which is capable of transforming documents between CSV, JSON and XML formats based on mappings expressed in the MSCR's internal format. We have also started to accumulate a test suite for mappings based on existing mapping implementations. Mapping engine is still very much a prototype, but it has demonstrated how to replicate existing case study requirements using the MSCR. The current transformation engine implementation is still in early prototype state, we are hoping to formalise the structure of the engine for a more robust implementation. Next steps for mappings include for example import and export functionality using SSSOM format.

When it comes to the content of the MSCR (schemas and crosswalks), the beta release implementation has focused on the "low-level" concrete document representations and their transformations. For example, how to turn a JSON document with a certain structure into another JSON document with another structure. When this thinking is expanded from tree-like structures into the realm of RDF graphs and schemas that are more akin to conceptual models, things will get even more complicated. A lot of discussions and planning has already been done in this area, but implementations are still missing. Support for RDF graphs and ontologies are key for example to the implementation of European Integration of National-Level services and Mathematics case studies.

- Source code for MSCR API Development <https://github.com/CSCfi/mscr-datamodel-api>
- Swagger UI for the backend APIs can be found at <https://mscr-test.rahtiapp.fi/swagger>.

5.3.2 MSCR UI Application Development

The developed version of MSCR UI Application consists of three core functionalities, Content registration, Search and Browse and Crosswalk Editor. The MSCR GUI application is currently in beta state with limited functionality and focused mainly on the MVP. For Authentication, EOSC AAI is integrated, and users can login to register and upload their content and search for content. Supported metadata schema file formats are CSV and JSON Schema. Users can also search for registered content through the UI. A primary version of the crosswalk editor supporting simple mappings is available. The available features in the UI are:

1. Supports registering of schemas/crosswalks and hosting them in the repository but not yet for registering of content hosted elsewhere.
2. Basic data management support: using PIDs, metadata, versioning and provenance information. The Beta version only provides fake PIDs that do not resolve.
3. Provides basic search functionality with limited facets.
4. Authentication through the EOSC AAI.
5. Data retention is not guaranteed. Any data can be deleted or modified.
6. The Crosswalk Editor only works with very simple mappings.

The beta release has been made available at <https://mscr-test.rahtiapp.fi>. This is a test environment that is used to host a "bleeding edge" version of the service, which is updated continuously without any notification. Another environment called the release environment will be provided early 2024 for more data intensive testing. For the release environment we will try to migrate data and communicate any changes to service to all case studies and demonstrators beforehand.

- Source code for MSCR UI Development <https://github.com/CSCfi/mscr-ui-monorepo>
- Beta Version of the MSCR UI is available at <https://mscr-test.rahtiapp.fi>.

6 EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR)

The data type registry, or DTR, is a service for users to register and explore data types. With the ambition of applying all measures towards a FAIR world, the DTR aims to make data types more findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. The DTR component consists of a type registry where types can be registered via a UI or through CRUD operations in a REST API or the DOIP. Each type is equipped with a handle PID. This persistent identifier has its own prefix hosted by the GWDG and allows the unambiguous identification of a data type for reference and reuse. Depending on the requirements for a type, different templates are provided to fulfil a wide range of applications. These templates allow the creation of schema types, measurement units, and basic taxonomy nodes.

To fulfil all requirements, some types require additional functionalities besides their mere registration and identifiability. As a part of the DTR component, an API is provided to provide those functionalities. These include the generation of validation schemas¹¹ for types describing schema elements and the retrieval of all types assigned to a taxonomy node or its children.

6.1 DTR Minimum Viable Product

As mentioned in the introduction, the DTR service consists of two sub-components, the type registry itself and the supporting TypeAPI. Since we were able to take advantage of available technology, namely the Cordra¹² software developed by CNRI¹³, we are able to offer the DTR itself with a rather high TRL, especially regarding the PID management due to Cordra’s inherent connection¹⁴ to the Handle¹⁵ system. As is shown in the table, the MVP for the beta release only includes basic authentication and authorization measures. Usage of external systems, like the EOSC AAI, are part of the HLR but not the MVP. The TypeAPI is considered to be in a pilot state.

Table 25 High-Level Roadmap of Data Type Registry MVP

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
Data Type Registry	Registration of Data Types and Type Schemas via UI	The Data Type Registry UI allows users to register data types via a form. Types can be exported as JSON objects. The UI also offers basic search capabilities and filtering options.	TLR 7	TLR 7	TRL 7	TRL 7	TRL 8	TRL 8
	Registration of Data Types and Type Schemas via API	Registration of new types can be performed via an API. Bulk imports are also possible.	TLR 7	TLR 7	TRL 7	TRL 7	TRL 8	TRL 8

¹¹ A schema, or metadata schema, is a complex data type constructed from 2 or more data types (e.g. schema elements), which can be complex or simple data types by themselves, for example the PIDINST metadata schema (i.e. complex data type) and the properties as schema elements (e.g. simple data types).

¹² <https://www.cordra.org/>

¹³ <https://www.cnri.reston.va.us/>

¹⁴ <https://www.cordra.org/documentation/design/handle-integration.html>

¹⁵ <https://www.handle.net/>

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
	PID Management	The Data Type Registry has an inherent connection to the handle system. Thus, each registered type has an associated handle PID under a custom prefix.	TLR 8	TLR 8	TRL 8	TRL 8	TRL 8	TRL 8
	Basic Authentication and Authorization User Management	Users and Groups can be managed via the UI. Users are added by an admin after requesting an account. Authenticated users can create access control lists for their types.	TLR 7	TLR 8				
	Prepared Schemas are complete and documented	Type are and Some templates are already prepared in the Data Type Registry. These allow the creation of schema types, measurement units, and basic taxonomy nodes.	TLR 4	TLR 5	TLR 5	TRL 6	TRL 7	TRL 7
TypeAPI	Generation of validation schemas for types representing schema objects	The generation of JSON schemas is an essential part of the interaction with schema types of the Type Registry. This allows the validation of objects that use the types in their metadata.	TLR 4	TLR 5	TRL 5	TRL 5	TRL 6	TRL 7
	Validating JSON Objects against registered types							
	Federated search over multiple registries	Different registries of types and type-like objects are harvested. Those are made accessible in a federated, faceted search.		TLR 4	TLR 4	TLR 4	TLR 5	TLR 5

6.2 DTR requirements overview

Table 26 DTR requirements overview

Case study	New	Restructuring	Accepted	Out-of-scope	Total
Climate Change	1	4	8	0	13
Social Sciences and Humanities	0	2	3	0	5
Mathematics	0	1	1	0	2

Case study	New	Restructuring	Accepted	Out-of-scope	Total
European integration of National-level Services	0	0	0	0	0
EOSC Service Providers & RDM Communities	0	1	3	0	4
Demonstrators					
B2INST	0	0	2	0	2
Extended MIME-Types	0	0	3	0	3
Typing metadata schema element and attribute values	0	0	4	0	4
Component					
User requirements	7	0	0	0	7

Table 27 DTR overview requirements MVP

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.42.DTR	Be able to request type information from the DTR given an object with a PID. Type information may also contain information on the unit of the values if the value has a unit.	CSCFC4EREQ-122
E4.5.3 DTR	This demonstrator shows the use of the DTR in typing metadata schema elements and attributes.	CSCFC4EREQ-77
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.47.DTR CC:	The DTR is able to handle unit information for data types to be able to annotate types with different units (e.g. for a temperature type we could have °C, °K or °F).	CSCFC4EREQ-456
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.49.DTR CC	When importing definitions from third parties (vocabularies, mime types, schema types, ...) the ownership of the types and the governance must be defined	CSCFC4EREQ-459
UR 4.5.2.6.1	DTR must support the registration and management (create, update, delete) of taxonomies as data types	CSCFC4EREQ-470
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.129_DTR	The DTR provides an HTTP REST API which allows B2SHARE to browse / search / update the set of basic data-types.	CSCFC4EREQ-129
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.125	This demonstrator shows the use of the DTR in typing metadata schema elements and attributes.	CSCFC4EREQ-125
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.15	Standard CRUD actions for data types	CSCFC4EREQ-43
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.17	Support a taxonomy on top of the specific data types	CSCFC4EREQ-45

6.3 DTR overview and the status of the developments

The development team of the GWDG responsible for the data type registry was able to take advantage of available technology, namely the Cordra software developed by CNRI. As a solution for the management of digital objects, we were able to use it as the core for the DTR component. Offering features such as the creation of digital objects based on user defined JSON schemas using a UI, REST or DOIP operations, a built-in connection to the handle system and subsequent generation of persistent identifiers for each object, and a basic solution for authentication and authorization, it offers already many of the tools necessary for a data type registry.

With the technological foundation given, the team was able to focus on conceptual work, namely the design of a general model to describe data types. In constant exchange with the case studies and demonstrators, we settled on a model for schema types that we deem easy to use while being sufficiently flexible to allow the creation of elaborate data types. In addition, a model for commonly used entities like measurement units and basic taxonomy nodes was created to allow the use of types in disciplines relying on more elaborate custom search facets. While maintaining generality and fulfilling specific requirements from the case studies has been a challenging task, adding the custom search facets feature has been implemented.

An instance of the cordra software provided with the mentioned models is currently hosted as a beta by the GWDG and can be found at the domain <https://typeregistry.lab.pidconsortium.net/>. Because the Cordra software already provisions an authorization mechanism integration with an external authorization system has not been prioritised for the beta release, therefore users will be required to request access to an account.

The MVP for the data type registry requires another subcomponent, namely the TypeAPI (i.e. DTR Toolkit). The TypeAPI is a Java Spring Boot based REST API providing additional services to use registered types. One main focus is the generation of JSON schemas to allow the validation of digital objects with respect to a schema type. The TypeAPI also offers the infrastructure to potentially harvest the contents of external type registries, but as of yet only small legacy registries are included. This functionality aims at creating a federated search environment for data types. Other endpoints of the TypeAPI allow the direct validation of an object using a generated schema of a type, and making an object designed with PIDs of types as keys human readable. All types harvested by the DTR Toolkit are indexed and thus searchable using different facets, allowing refined exploration. This search indexer can directly be accessed by other tools to allow inclusion of registered data types in their services. The beta of the TypeAPI can be accessed via <https://typeapi.lab.pidconsortium.net>.

7 EOSC Research Activity Identifier (RAiD)

A Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) is a globally unique, persistent identifier (PID) for research projects or activities. It consists of a unique identifier (a DOI handle) and a metadata record. The metadata record links various information sources (e.g. contributors, organisations, grants, instruments, publications, datasets, etc.) to the project metadata via their own PIDs where available (e.g. ORCiDs, RORs, Crossref Grant IDs, DOIs, etc.). RAiDs also contain project information not found elsewhere, such as project title, start date, description and subject, but does not duplicate information found elsewhere. RAiDs can also be linked to one another using arbitrary qualified relationships so that (e.g.) subprojects can be created.

To date, software development has focused on producing the core RAiD Service. This software allows creation, management, editing, and retrieval of RAiDs (DOI as identifier plus the metadata record) via either an Application Programming Interface (API) or graphical user interfaces (GUIs).

7.1 RAiD Minimum Viable Product

The RAiD MVP demonstrates core functionality of the system. Case studies can use it to explore RAiD in a ‘demonstration’ environment (metadata records will not be maintained long-term). Specifically, case study participants can:

- Mint a RAiD using a DataCite DOI, which will also populate DataCite metadata with a subset of the RAiD metadata.
- List, create, resolve, and edit RAiDs via a stable API¹⁶ that will not change between now and production (other than the possible addition of new endpoints).
- Utilise a stable and complete metadata schema¹⁷ when minting RAiDs.

This functionality will provide case studies with an understanding of the system and allow the development of integrations and good practices.

Table 28 High-Level Roadmap of RAiD MVP

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
RAiD Registration Agency Service	Mint DOI to serve as RAiD Name (identifier)	When a RAiD is created, access a DataCite Local Handle Server to acquire a DOI for the RAiD. Populate DataCite core metadata from RAiD metadata.	TRL 2	TRL 6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
	Create RAiD Metadata Record via API	Provide API for creation, editing, and management of RAiDs (access control via API key and, where applicable, local UI feeding into RAiD). Support the use of API keys at the necessary granularity to control access. All elements of the metadata record can be manipulated via the API.	TRL 5	TRL 7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8

¹⁶ <https://api.demo.raid.org.au/swagger-ui/index.html#/raido-stable-v1>

¹⁷ <https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/>

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
		Validate component PIDs and other metadata elements where possible.						
	RAiD metadata schema complete and stable.	The schema that the RAiD Metadata Record uses is complete, stable, and well-documented.	TRL 6	TRL 7	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8

7.2 RAiD requirements overview

Table 29 RAiD Requirements overview

Case study	New	Restructuring	Accepted	Out-of-scope	Total
Climate Change	1	3	6	0	10
Social Sciences and Humanities	0	0	0	0	0
Mathematics	0	0	2	0	2
European integration of National-level Services	0	0	7	0	7
EOSC Service Providers & RDM Communities	1	0	0	0	1
Component					
User stories	19	18	12	0	49
Service specifications	6	6	6	0	18
Functional specifications	4	10	12	0	26
Functional requirements	4	8	9	0	21
User requirements	9	21	14	0	44
Operational requirements	1	3	1	0	5
Integration with core components	0	0	5	0	5
Non functional requirements	2	9	3	0	14

Table 30 RAiD overview requirements MVP

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.19.RAiD CC: RAiD hierarchy and metadata	As an author of IPCC assessment reports I want to be able to explore all datasets created for the CMIP6 project in one place. I want to be able to see who generated which data, when the data was generated and in which organization. Furthermore, I need information on the project context (related projects in other hierarchy layers) the data was generated in to be able to correctly cite the data.	CSCFC4EREQ-95
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.20.RAiD CC: Linked RAiDs and data PIDs	As an author of IPCC assessment reports I want to be able to find/explore research projects related to a research project I used data from. I want to be linked to the produced/used data for the project, so that I do not need to search for the data elsewhere.	CSCFC4EREQ-96
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.21.RAiD CC: Relevant project metadata in RAiD to improve workflow	As an author of IPCC assessment reports I want to be able to find all information on a model result I am using. I want to find e.g. funder information without needing to ask another person, since these speeds up my work.	CSCFC4EREQ-97
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.22.RAiD CC: Link to RAiDs from other metadata	As a researcher I want to be able to link a metadata object from my data's metadata, containing information on the project I generated the data in not found anywhere else, like e.g. funding. Therefore, I need some kind of persistent identifier and resolving mechanism.	CSCFC4EREQ-98

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.26.RAID CC: RAID ownership transfer	As a research institute supporting other research institutes (e.g. DKRZ) I need to be able to create RAIDs for projects and then transfer the ownership of the projects to other parties at a later point in time. When the ownership takes place the target institute must accept the transfer, since as an institution I do not want to have RAIDs assigned to me, which I do not want to be affiliated with. The RAIDs pending for ownership transfer should not appear in the public profile of my institution.	CSCFC4EREQ-102
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.53: Integration of RAID in National CRIS systems	As a national CRIS service provider, I want to operationalize RAID in national CRIS domain, e.g. adopt RAID as de facto project identifier in national systems and possibility to mint them while working on master data of project information from e.g. research organizations.	CSCFC4EREQ-160
WP7.T7.1_Case_R.4_T4.4: EOSC Research Activity Identifier Service (RAiD)	The API will return the related digital object for a given PID coming from swMATH	CSCFC4EREQ-144
WP4.T4.4_RAiD_R.2: GUI Landing Page	GUI (e.g., web application or static web pages) for resolving a RAiD handle and displaying that RAiD's metadata content, thus providing a RAiD 'landing page'.	CSCFC4EREQ-328
WP4.T4.4_RAiD_R.5: Retrieve RAiD by Metadata - API	Search and retrieve RAIDs based on metadata content, Registration Agency, Organisation, Service Point, or User via API, returning handle and metadata.	CSCFC4EREQ-304
WP4.T4.4_RAiD_R.6: Retrieve RAiD by Metadata - GUI	Search and retrieve RAIDs based on metadata content, Registration Agency, Organisation, Service Point, or User via GUI, displaying handle and metadata	
WP4.T4.4_RAiD_R.27: Auto-Export RAIDs Related to PIDs	Automatically export RAIDs to external PIDs related to the RAiD.	CSCFC4EREQ-326
WP4.T4.4_RAiD_R.2: RAiD Harvesting by PIDGraph	Support RAiD harvesting by PIDGraph	CSCFC4EREQ-351

7.3 RAiD overview and the status of the developments

We aimed to deliver four core components of RAiD for the MVP. Two were successfully delivered at TRL 7: an API to create, edit, resolve, and list RAIDs¹⁸ associated with a single instance of the RAiD Service software ('raido-stable-v1' endpoints), and a stable / mature metadata schema¹⁹. The final MVP component is nearing completion to TRL 7 but has not yet reached it: implementation of DOIs as RAiD identifiers. Minting of DataCite DOIs from the RAiD Service software is currently in testing (i.e., deployed to our 'test' server and not minting 'real' DOIs). Until then, the demo and production environments are still minting generic handles. This level of maturity is sufficient for the Case Studies to begin working with the system using the demo server, and we have begun granting them access to that environment (transition from Handles to DOIs will have little impact on the end-user experience). We anticipate deployment to our demo and production servers by the end of the year, pending some additional development that DataCite needs to complete to allow RAiD's multi-dot prefixes.

¹⁸ <https://api.demo.raid.org.au/swagger-ui/index.html#/raido-stable-v1>

¹⁹ <https://metadata.raid.org/>

8 EOSC PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR)

The increasing use of PIDs to reference all types of research results is a major step forward in meeting requirements for the FAIRness of (research) data. Although this trend is very welcome, new challenges arise in processing these PIDs and integrating them into different research processes. The biggest difficulty is the multitude of systems used to create and maintain PIDs. The challenge is to know which system is responsible for the resolution process, the process that provides the referenced (meta-)data for a PID. A uniform interface that allows PIDs from different systems to be resolved can simplify various processes. The PID Meta Resolver is such an interface. Over the course of the project, the PID Meta Resolver will integrate more PID systems.

The PID Meta Resolver is a generalised resolver for mapping keys into values. The PID Meta Resolver will know where to “route” different types of identifiers – e.g. DOI or URN:NBN. The main goal of the PID Meta Resolver is to improve machine-based data processing and to allow getting digital object information without in-depth knowledge of the resolution mechanism of different PID systems. This enhances the compilation and analysis of data collections originating not only from different sources but also referenced by different PID systems.

8.1 PIDMR Minimum Viable Product

The beta version of the FAIRCORE4EOSC PID Meta Resolver is a deployed version with the minimum features to satisfy early adopters and solicit feedback for future product development. Via an easy-to-use Web UI it demonstrates the main features of the service such as:

- 1) PID resolution to different supported resolution types (metadata, resource and landing page)
- 2) PID Providers information and finally
- 3) an informational widget - like box to guide the user in the PID ecosystem.

The PID Meta Resolver is a service based on

- The Meta Resolver backend²⁰ (GWDG) developed based on the Handle Software and Handle Proxy Server, aims to provide the technological foundation for the resolving mechanism and implements an API for recognizing and resolving persistent identifiers from different providers via a single endpoint.
- The Metaresolver UI²¹ - PIDMR-UI (GRNET) [2], is a web-application, created using the React JavaScript framework. Metaresolver UI provides the main user interface for exploring and resolving PIDs.
- The Metaresolver API^{22,23} - PIDMR API (GRNET), is built using the Quarkus framework. It is designed to resolve Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for various PID Providers. It uses the endpoint provided by the Meta Resolver to serve the different implemented endpoints.

The beta version of the Meta Resolver implements the following capabilities/functionalities.

Table 31 High-Level Roadmap of PID Metaresolver MVP

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
Meta Resolver Core	Resolve PIDs from different systems	A Handle based resolving mechanism that allows resolution of many persistent identifiers over a single resolving endpoint.	TRL4	TRL5	TRL6	TRL7		

²⁰ Metaresolver Backend - <https://pidmr.lab.pidconsortium.net>

²¹ Metaresolver UI - <https://pidmr.devel.argo.grnet.gr>

²² Metaresolver API description - <https://apimr.devel.argo.grnet.gr>

²³ Metaresolver API Swagger UI - <https://apimr.devel.argo.grnet.gr/swagger-ui/>

Sub-component	Capability/Function	Short description	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
	<p>Allows parameter based query options</p> <p>Function to redirect to landing page</p> <p>Function to provide meta data</p> <p>Function that allows access to the resource</p> <p>Resolving Handle, DOI, ARK, arXiv, URN:NBN, SWH and Zenodo PIDs</p>							
PID Meta Resolver UI	<p>Resolves single PIDs in a WebUI</p> <p>Validates PID formats</p> <p>Connects to the Meta Resolver API</p> <p>Sends request to Meta Resolver API</p>	<p>Additional services to aid human users in the use of the meta resolver by providing a user interface and listing all available service providers.</p>	TRL4	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8
PID Meta Resolver API	<p>Accepts requests from the Meta Resolver API</p> <p>Provides the logic for validating PID formats</p> <p>Provides data base with service provider information</p> <p>Sends requests to the Meta Resolver Core to resolve PIDs</p>	<p>Middle layer between the Meta Resolver UI and the Meta Resolver Core. The Meta Resolver API includes some logic, e.g., validating input parameters or checking for a valid PID format.</p>	TRL4	TRL6				

8.2 PIDMR Requirements overview

Table 32 PIDMR Requirements overview

Case study	New	Restructuring	Accepted	Out-of-scope	Total
Social Sciences and Humanities	0	0	3	2	5
Mathematics	0	0	2	0	2
Component					
User requirements	1	2	13	0	16
Functional specifications	0	0	6	0	6
Service specifications	1	6	8	0	15
Operational specifications	0	0	2	0	2
Integration with core components	2	0	0	0	2
Non functional requirements	0	0	4	0	4

Table 33 PIDMR overview requirements MVP

Requirement	Short description	Reference
Deploy a ui for PID MetaResolver	the user needs a UI to understand how the service is working. In order to do that we need to deploy a new UI so as to support the service.	CSCFC4EREQ-355
List of identifiers supported	The user needs a page to understand which identifiers the PIDMR supports	CSCFC4EREQ-356
Metaresolver should understand the different providers	The MetaResolver should understand the different types of PID based on the syntax (the first characters of the string) or the resolver address in the HTTP URI representation of the PID, i.e. 10. for DOIs, 21. for EPIC Handles, SWH": for Software heritage software etc.	CSCFC4EREQ-393
Metaresolver should support the schema and structure of PID	The system should support the schema, the structure of the information a PID resolution system supports.	CSCFC4EREQ-360
The system should resolve Handle PIDs	The system should resolve Handles.	CSCFC4EREQ-364
The system should resolve DOI PIDs	The system should resolve DOIs.	CSCFC4EREQ-363
The system should resolve URN:NBN PIDs	The system should resolve URN:NBN, ie. URN:NBN:DE, URN:NBN:FI	CSCFC4EREQ-365
The system should resolve SoftWare Heritage PIDs	The system should resolve Software Heritage PIDs	CSCFC4EREQ-366
The system should resolve arXiv PIDs	The system should resolve arXiv PIDs	CSCFC4EREQ-530
The system should resolve ARK PIDs	The system should resolve ARK PIDs like ark:/67531/metaph346793	CSCFC4EREQ-531

8.3 PIDMR overview and the status of the developments

In the scope of MS24, a set of comprehensive requirements/specifications were defined for providing user services, functional and non-functional capabilities of the Meta Resolvers^{24,25}. Based on these requirements,

²⁴https://tt.eduuni.fi/sites/csc-rdi-files/FAIRCORE4EOSC/WP1%20Project%20coordination%20and%20strategic%20alignment/Submitted%20FAIRCORE4EOSC%20Milestones/FAIRCORE4EOSC_MS24%20PID%20Meta%20Resolver%20specifications.pdf

²⁵<https://wiki.eduuni.fi/pages/viewpage.action?spaceKey=cscRDIcollaboration&title=Requirement+Analysis++PID+Meta+Resolver>

a rough C4Model was developed^{26,27}, which served as the basis for further development. Development is ongoing in different teams for the subcomponents.

8.3.1 PIDMR Metaresolver

The Metaresolver is the main component that is responsible for the resolution of a PID and the presentation of a landing page, metadata or the underlying resource of the PID. A proxy server was set up based on the Handle Software which provides resolving service for the following PID providers in the current release:

- Archival Resource Key (ARK PID)
- arXiv PID
- Software Heritage persistent IDentifiers (SWHID)
- German urn:nbn PID (urn:nbn:de)
- Finnish urn:nbn PID (urn:nbn:fi)
- zenodo PID
- Handles
- DOIs

The proxy server of the Meta Resolver is available at <https://pidmr.lab.pidconsortium.net>, but resolving is possible via any handle resolving service using the handle PID 21.T11973/MR@ followed by the PID to be resolved. The service determines the structure of the information that can be expected from a resolution request and thus provides the possibility to request the landing page, metadata or resource of the digital object specified via the PID. The resolver is able to recognize the PID type entered for resolution and knows where to route the request in order to get the requested information. The list of potential PID providers is easily extendable so that a new PID provider can be onboarded without much effort. Performance testing based on determination of the dependency of the resolving performance on the number of providers were carried out which indicate no significant performance fluctuation. A detailed report about this has been documented²⁸.

8.3.2 PIDMR Metaresolver UI

The Metaresolver UI (PIDMR-UI) is a web-application, created using the React JavaScript framework. Metaresolver UI provides the main user interface for resolving PIDs. It is the first client that validates and tests the use of the Metaresolver API. The current development instance resides at <https://pidmr.devel.argo.grnet.gr> and uses the Metaresolver API (PIDMR-API)²⁹ as backend.

The UI consists of two main views:

- The persistent identifier resolver UI: In this view the user can enter a PID of any of the supported types and choose to resolve it in one of three ways: a) Get PID's landing page b) Get PID's metadata, c) Get PID's resource itself. For each Provider the Metaresolver UI supports one or many of the above resolving modes. The Metaresolver UI also includes an informational box which responds interactively to the user input and displays information about the current input and suggestions. This is a library of persistent identifiers guidance documentation that tries to help the end user understand the use of PIDs, validates the PID before resolving it and guides the user on how to correctly use it.
- Supported Providers: In this view the UI displays a dynamic list (retrieved from the backend api) with all Supported PID Providers / PID types. Currently this page presents the following information a) name/prefix used b) short description, c) supported resolving modes.

²⁶ <https://wiki.eduuni.fi/download/attachments/303282924/PIDMR-C4-Level1-20221221.png>

²⁷ <https://wiki.eduuni.fi/download/attachments/303282924/PIDMR-C4-Level2-20221221.png>

²⁸ <https://wiki.eduuni.fi/display/cscRD/collaboration/Performance+Measurement+for+PIDMR>

²⁹ <https://pidmr.lab.pidconsortium.net>

8.3.3 PIDMR Metaresolver API

The Metaresolver API is built using the Quarkus framework. It is designed to resolve Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) from various PID Providers. It redirects to the Metaresolver that is responsible for the final resolution of the PIDs. The API is using specific regular expressions to understand the type of Provider and validate the Persistent identifier. The API understands the type of PID and then resolves it by requesting resolvable URLs from an external handler, the Metaresolver. The API supports three methods to resolve a PID: retrieve the resource, resolve the metadata record of the PID, or go to the landing page.

The API provide the following 3 main features:

- PID Providers: The API supports the management of PID Providers. An administrator is able to manage (add, update, delete) the data of a PID Provider. The API also displays the list of PID Providers, each responsible for validating specific PIDs based on predefined regular expressions. An authorised user may also get the details of the PID Provider.
- Resolve PIDs: For each resolution method, the API requests the corresponding resolvable URL from the Metaresolver. By default, this operation returns a JSON response containing the URL resolving the PID. A user may immediately resolve the PID by using the 'redirect' parameter since the API redirects you to the resolving page. The different types of resolution are as follows.
 - Resource Resolution: Resolving a PID using the resource resolution method provides the URL to the associated resource.
 - Metadata Resolution: Metadata resolution returns the URL to the metadata associated with a PID.
 - Landing Page Resolution: This resolution method provides the URL to the landing page associated with a PID.
- Validate PIDs: This operation checks the validity of each identifier. Every Provider has a regex based on which the validation is performed.

The Metaresolver API resides at <https://apimr.devel.argo.grnet.gr> and the documentation of the API can be reached at <https://apimr.devel.argo.grnet.gr/swagger-ui/>.

Conclusion

Development has progressed well in all subcomponents and the EOSC PID Meta Resolver is on track to deliver a beta release at the end of November 2023.

9 Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC)

The FAIRCORE4EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC) components aim at implementing the recommendations from the Scholarly Infrastructures of Research Software (SIRS) report³⁰ to archive, reference, describe, and cite research software artifacts. Integrating research software into the scholarly ecosystem alongside publications and data. This beta release report encapsulates the progress made within the project, particularly in achieving the objectives outlined in Work Package 6 (WP6).

Within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, WP6 is dedicated to the development of tools and services essential for the archival, reference, description, and citation of research software artifacts. The primary aim is creating a cohesive interconnection between scholarly repositories, publishers, and aggregators. This is achieved through integration with the Software Heritage universal source code archive, utilising the CodeMeta standard and the Software Hash identifiers (SWHID).

The beta release marks a significant milestone in the FAIRCORE4EOSC journey. It serves as a tangible representation of the progress made toward the realization of the SIRS report's vision. The tools and services unveiled under WP6 are a testament to the commitment of the collaborative effort in shaping the future of scholarly communication.

The RSAC (Research Software APIs and Connectors) component is structured into six sub-components, each dedicated to specific infrastructure such as:

- T6.1 Scholarly repositories:
 - InvenioRDM - SWH APIs and connectors (CERN)
 - DataVerse - SWH APIs and connectors (DANS)
- T6.2. Publishers:
 - Dagstuhl - SWH APIs and connectors (LZI)
 - Episciences - SWH APIs and connectors (INRIA)
- T6.3 Aggregators:
 - swMATH - SWH APIs and connectors (FIZ)
 - OpenAIRE - SWH APIs and connectors (OPENAIRE)

This division allows for a focused and comprehensive approach to developing tools and services essential for archiving, referencing, describing, and citing research software artifacts within distinct domains of the scholarly ecosystem. The following table lists the sub-components development location, documentation and beta demo:

Table 34 Information related to the RSAC sub-components

Sub-component	Code repo	Documentation	Beta demo
InvenioRDM - SWH APIs and connectors (CERN)	https://github.com/inveniosoftware/invenio-swh/	https://help.zenodo.org/docs/deposit/create-new-upload/	https://sandbox.zenodo.org/
DataVerse - SWH APIs and connectors (DANS)	https://github.com/DANS-KNAW		https://swh.dansdemo.nl/
Dagstuhl - SWH APIs and connectors (LZI)	https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/beta-faircore4eosc	https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/beta-faircore4eosc/blob/main/api/Modules/SwhApi/README.md	https://faircore4eosc.dagstuhl.de/

³⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Scholarly infrastructures for research software – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture Task Force (TF) SIRS*, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/28598>

Sub-component	Code repo	Documentation	Beta demo
Episciences - SWH APIs and connectors (INRIA)	https://github.com/CCSDForge/episciences/issues?q=is%3Aissue+is%3Aopen+label%3AFAIRCORE4EOSC	https://doc.episciences.org/	https://epijinfo.episciences.org
swMATH - SWH APIs and connectors (FIZ)	https://github.com/MaRDI4NFDI/swMATH4EOSC	https://github.com/MaRDI4NFDI/swMATH4EOSC/blob/main/Documenation_of_swMATH_TABLES.md	https://staging.swMATH.org/wiki/Sagemath
OpenAIRE - SWH APIs and connectors (OPENAIRE)	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/beta/dhp-workflows/dhp-swh	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/	https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu

9.1 RSAC Minimum Viable Product

The beta version of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC) is a deployed version with the minimum features in the staging instances of each partner to enable a testing period with beta testers. With the first testing period we will gather feedback for future product development.

The beta version of the RSAC components implements the capabilities / functionalities in the following table at M18. Specifically, the table also contains the maturity level (TRL) of each sub-component capability/function in different time points of the project lifetime.

Table 35 High-Level Roadmap of RSAC MVP

Sub-component	Capability / Function	Short description of MVP	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
InvenioRDM	Archive	InvenioRDM automatically archives software source code in SWH. Demonstrated in the Zenodo sandbox environment.	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9	TRL9
	Reference	The SWHID and DOI are both exposed on the record landing page.	TRL4	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9	TRL9	TRL9
	Describe	Software-specific fields available in the Zenodo sandbox environment.	TRL4	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9	TRL9	TRL9
	Cite	Export formats (BibTeX, CSL and CodeMeta formats) are available in Zenodo sandbox environment.	TRL4	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9	TRL9	TRL9
Dataverse	Archive	The deposit pipeline and user interface developed by DANS will allow the deposit of both data and software in a single workflow, combining the metadata requested from the end user to be compliant with the mandatory elements of both Dataverse and CodeMeta. The deposit pipeline makes use of Sword 2.0 and deposits data to Dataverse and software to Software Heritage.	TRL4	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Reference	References will include cross-linking of the DOI issues by Dataverse and the SWHID issued by Software Heritage.	TRL4	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Describe	Dataverse metadata will describe the dataset using a minimum of Dataverse and DataCite metadata. Software will be	TRL4	TRL6	TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8

Sub-component	Capability / Function	Short description of MVP	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
		described using a minimum based on CodeMeta.						
	Cite	Citations of both the dataset and the code will be available as standardised versions accessible via the respective PIDs.	TRL4	TRL4	TRL5	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8
Dagstuhl	Archive	Automate the archival in Software Heritage of the source code of artifacts associated with research articles.	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9		
	Reference	Expose the corresponding SWHID on the journal's publication record.	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9		
	Describe	Enable the deposit and retrieval in Software Heritage of curated metadata for software associated to publications.		TRL5	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9
	Cite	Deposit and retrieve the preferred citation information for software associated with publications; export citation information in one or more of the common open citation formats (BibLaTeX, CSL, codemeta.json).		TRL5	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9
Episciences	Archive	The source code is already archived on Software Heritage	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Reference	Expose the corresponding SWHID on the journal's publication record.	TRL4	TRL8	TRL9	TRL9	TRL9	TRL9
	Describe	Enable the deposit and retrieval in Software Heritage of curated metadata for software associated with publications.	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9	TRL9
	Cite	Deposit and retrieve the preferred citation information for software associated with publications; export citation information in one or more of the common open citation formats (BibLaTeX, CSL, codemeta.json).	TRL4	TRL4	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9
swMATH	Archive	Extract references to software from research articles and trigger archival of source code known to swMATH	TRL4	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8	TRL9
	Reference	Expose the corresponding origin (URL) and SWHID	TRL4	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8	TRL9
	Describe	Deposit and retrieve metadata for the software artifacts in Software Heritage	TRL4	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8	TRL9
	Cite	Deposit and/or retrieve preferred citation information for the software artifacts in Software Heritage; export citation information in one or more of the common open citation formats (BibLaTeX, CSL, codemeta.json)	TRL4	TRL7	TRL8	TRL8	TRL8	TRL9
OpenAIRE	Archive	To trigger the archival of software artifacts which are already included in OpenAIRE (since they have been identified based on their mentions in research articles) but missing from SWH. SWHIDs will be acquired for the respective software artifacts.		TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Reference	To maintain and expose the SWHIDs for all the software artefact records maintained by OpenAIRE, where applicable.		TRL6	TRL6	TRL7	TRL7	TRL8
	Describe	To deposit missing software artefact metadata in SWH and to retrieve software		TRL3	TRL4	TRL5	TRL6	TRL7

Sub-component	Capability / Function	Short description of MVP	M12	M18	M22	M26	M30	M34
		artefact descriptions from SWH to be included in the respective OpenAIRE records.						
	Cite	To export citation information in BibTex and codemeta.json.		TRL5	TRL5	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8

9.2 RSAC requirements overview

9.2.1 Scholarly repositories

9.2.1.1 InvenioRDM-SWH Research Software API and Connectors

Integration of InvenioRDM (Scholarly Repository) with Software Heritage. Overall, the purpose is to develop tools and services for archival, reference, description and citation of research software artifacts, by implementing the key recommendations of the EOSC SIRS report to interconnect scholarly repositories with the Software Heritage universal source code archive, using the CodeMeta standard, and the Software Heritage intrinsic identifiers (SWHID).

Table 36 RSAC-InvenioRDM overview requirements

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP6.T6.1_RSAC_BETA_InvenioRDM_Archive	Archive: deposit bundle of source code into repository, register already SWH-archived source code in a repository & deposit a new release of source code into a repository	CSCFC4EREQ-472
WP6.T6.1_RSAC_BETA_InvenioRDM_Reference	Reference: retrieve a persistent extrinsic and intrinsic identifier from the repository, so that it will reference the record and source code artifacts	CSCFC4EREQ-473
WP6.T6.1_RSAC_BETA_InvenioRDM_Describe	Describe software using software specific metadata, retrieve metadata export for deposit in repository & update metadata of software in repository	CSCFC4EREQ-474
WP6.T6.1_RSAC_BETA_InvenioRDM_Cite	Cite: retrieve a citation export format from the repository	CSCFC4EREQ-475

9.2.1.2 Dans-DataVerse prototype - SWH Research Software API and Connectors

Integration of Dataverse (scholarly repository) with Software Heritage in a DANS prototype to deposit software and data. DANS is building a DANS deposit form for researchers to deposit their data and metadata into a relevant DANS DataStation (Dataverse).

This SWH connector will use the DANS deposit form to trigger automated source code archiving at SWH if specific software metadata fields are available (rule engine based), while other related metadata and data objects will be deposited into a vanilla Dataverse instance. The rule engine and the deposit form are currently under further development and are also in use by other services provided by DANS. The connection to SWH to request archiving or retrieve the SWHID has been implemented into the DANS Deposit form and included in this BETA release. By using the SWH 'swh-deposit' package, the deposit form is also reporting on the current deposit status, SWH and Dataverse, after a deposit request by the user.

This component deposits the relevant research software artifacts (source code, related datasets and their metadata) to Dataverse (DV) and Software Heritage (SWH). In doing so, the obtained SWHID will be reflected in the record maintained by the Dataverse repository and vice versa for the extrinsic Dataverse PID in the SWH metadata.

Table 37 RSAC-DataVerse overview requirements

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP6.T6.1_RSAC_BETA_DataVerse_Archive	Archive: Deposit software code related dataset(s) and archive the related software code in a SCM system at once, including their metadata from one deposit form.	CSCFC4EREQ-477
WP6.T6.1_RSAC_BETA_DataVerse_Reference	Reference: An API for the provisioning of metadata and references to code for long-term preservation in Software Heritage. The code is linked to a dataset and/or other research objects being deposited. Needs to return a PID (SWHID) for inclusion into PID graphs and provenance information in DataVerse.	CSCFC4EREQ-478
WP6.T6.1_RSAC_BETA_DataVerse_Describe	Describe: An API for retrieving metadata in an agreed schema (CodeMeta) from Software Heritage based on a SWHID	CSCFC4EREQ-479
WP6.T6.1_RSAC_BETA_DataVerse_Cite	Cite: obtain a citation in one or more standardised formats (specific formats to be confirmed)	CSCFC4EREQ-480

9.2.2 Publishers

9.2.2.1 Dagstuhl -SWH Research Software API and Connectors

Dagstuhl has developed its own SWH connector API managing all interactions with the SWH-side; the API is capable of triggering automated archiving requests as well as tracking relevant archive status updates. The API-archive functionality has extended archive requests to address specific paths within repositories rather than the main "base repository". The API-reference functionality integrates relevant SWHIDs to LaTeX macro's to reference SW on our published papers. The API-archive and reference features have been integrated in the Dagstuhl internal system and currently in production. With regards to Describe and Cite functionality, Dagstuhl has developed a user-friendly interface to export/import codemeta.json. Within the same interface, we have also developed CodeMeta conversions to other schemes (currently, BibTeX, BibLaTeX, and DataCite).

Table 38 Table 38. RSAC-Dagstuhl overview requirements

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP6.T6.2_RSAC_BETA_Dagstuhl_Archive	Archive: automate the archival in Software Heritage of the source code of artifacts associated with research articles.	CSCFC4EREQ-481
WP6.T6.2_RSAC_BETA_Dagstuhl_Reference	Reference: expose the corresponding SWHID on the journal's publication record.	CSCFC4EREQ-482
WP6.T6.2_RSAC_BETA_Dagstuhl_Describe	Describe: enable the deposit and retrieval in Software Heritage of curated metadata for software associated with publications.	CSCFC4EREQ-483
WP6.T6.2_RSAC_BETA_Dagstuhl_Cite	Cite: deposit and retrieve the preferred citation information for software associated with publications; export citation information in one or more of the common open citation formats (BibLaTeX, CSL, codemeta.json).	CSCFC4EREQ-484

9.2.2.2 Episciences-SWH Research Software API and Connectors

Develop APIs and connectors between Episciences and Software Heritage to a workflow specific to software submission. This has been implemented in a testing environment: authors can now add source code to their paper submission (using an "add software" option). Reviewers have access to the source code in the peer-reviewing form and the corresponding SWHID is displayed on the journal's publication record, where an iframe also displays the software source code available in Software Heritage.

Table 39 RSAC-Episciences overview requirements

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP6.T6.2_RSAC_BETA_Episciences_Archive	Archive: Source code is already archived on Software Heritage	CSCFC4EREQ-486
WP6.T6.2_RSAC_BETA_Episciences_Reference	Reference: expose the corresponding SWHID on the journal's publication record.	CSCFC4EREQ-487
WP6.T6.2_RSAC_BETA_Episciences_Describe	Describe: enable the deposit and retrieval in Software Heritage of curated metadata for software associated with publications.	CSCFC4EREQ-488
WP6.T6.2_RSAC_BETA_Episciences_Cite	Cite: deposit and retrieve the preferred citation information for software associated with publications; export citation information in one or more of the common open citation formats (BibLaTeX, CSL, codemeta.json).	CSCFC4EREQ-489

9.2.3 Aggregators

9.2.3.1 swMATH-SWH Research Software API and Connectors

This component implements an API and connectors between swMATH and Software Heritage to support archival, reference, description and citation of mathematical software artifacts leveraging the CodeMeta standard, and the Software Heritage intrinsic identifiers (SWHID). A MediaWiki instance serves to expose the swMATH database content. swMATH built a prototype to make its software metadata available in CodeMeta and DataCite formats, developed the functionalities to trigger source code archiving, and is currently working to collect the SWHIDs, which will be accessible to the users. Aside from that, a close collaboration has started with the SWH team to submit and ingest a first metadata-only deposit.

Table 40 RSAC-swMATH overview requirements

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP6.T6.3_RSAC_BETA_swMATH_Archive	Archive: Create a script to trigger archival using search API of SWH	CSCFC4EREQ-418
WP6.T6.3_RSAC_BETA_swMATH_Reference	Reference: expose the corresponding origin (URL) and SWHID	CSCFC4EREQ-495
WP6.T6.3_RSAC_BETA_swMATH_Describe	Describe: deposit and retrieve metadata for the software artifacts in Software Heritage	CSCFC4EREQ-496
WP6.T6.3_RSAC_BETA_swMATH_Cite	Cite: deposit and/or retrieve preferred citation information for the software artifacts in Software Heritage; export citation information in one or more of the common open citation formats (BibLaTeX, CSL, codemeta.json)	CSCFC4EREQ-497

9.2.3.2 OpenAire-SWH Research Software API and Connectors

This component implements an API and connectors between OpenAIRE and Software Heritage to support archival, reference, description and citation of research software artifacts leveraging the CodeMeta standard, and the Software Heritage intrinsic identifiers (SWHID). A set of workflows are built in the OpenAIRE Graph provision process to support the integration of the OpenAIRE Graph with Software Heritage (SWH). Specifically, software repositories, present in the OpenAIRE Graph but missing from SWH, are submitted for archival via the SWH API. Furthermore, OpenAIRE collects SWH identifiers for software entities in the Graph and will expose them through its next public dumps. OpenAIRE Explore will also enable users to export citation information for software using BibTex.

Table 41 RSAC-OpenAire overview requirements

Requirement	Short description	Reference
WP6.T6.3_RSAC_BETA_OpenAire_Archive	Archive: To trigger the archival of software artifacts which are already included in OpenAIRE (since they have been identified based on their mentions in research articles) but missing from SWH. SWHIDs will be acquired for the respective software artifacts.	CSCFC4EREQ-491
WP6.T6.3_RSAC_BETA_OpenAire_Reference	Reference: To maintain and expose the SWHIDs for all the software artifact records maintained by OpenAIRE, where applicable.	CSCFC4EREQ-492
WP6.T6.3_RSAC_BETA_OpenAire_Describe	Describe: To deposit missing software artifact metadata in SWH and to retrieve software artifact descriptions from SWH to be included in the respective OpenAIRE records.	CSCFC4EREQ-493
WP6.T6.3_RSAC_BETA_OpenAire_Cite	Cite: To export citation information in BibTex and codemeta.json.	CSCFC4EREQ-494

9.3 RSAC overview and the status of the developments

The sub-component leads are developing the functionalities as part of an iterative process that started following the establishment of the specifications, in January 2023.

In October 2023, INRIA organised an on-site short sprint with a representative from each sub-component team. During the sprint, each sub-component lead verified the functionalities and their adequacy with the specifications. Each has also identified the immediate next steps to be implemented in the upcoming BETA RELEASE, due at the end of November 2023.

Following the November 2023 BETA-RELEASE, we will collect user feedback and proceed with development towards the next iteration.

Status of development in this deliverable was captured on November 21st.

9.3.1 Scholarly repositories

9.3.1.1 InvenioRDM

Work done:

- Custom fields feature developed to allow implementation of software fields - defined data model, deposit form widgets, record landing page rendering and export formats integration. See documentation³¹
- Software fields defined using the custom fields feature³²
- BibTeX³³ and CSL³⁴ export formats integrated
- Launched Zenodo on InvenioRDM (October 13) which is required in order to launch any of the InvenioRDM-SWH features in both sandbox and production. We experienced major issues with the upgrade and have spent most of October with all available resources to minimise the impact which have delayed us in the tasks to integrate the automatic archiving of software in SWH.
- Selected and imported programming language vocabulary (from GitHub).
- Updated BibTex/CSL/JSON-LD export formats after user-feedback on Zenodo.
- Implemented deposit from repository into universal source code archive.
- Implemented display of SWHID on record landing page.

³¹ https://inveniordm.docs.cern.ch/customize/metadata/custom_fields/records/

³² https://github.com/inveniosoftware/invenio-rdm-records/blob/2e363f35c1df91a8ba92b28a7fb26035b857d976/invenio_rdm_records/contrib/codemeta/custom_fields.py

³³ https://github.com/inveniosoftware/invenio-rdm-records/tree/2e363f35c1df91a8ba92b28a7fb26035b857d976/invenio_rdm_records/resources/serializers/bibtex

³⁴ https://github.com/inveniosoftware/invenio-rdm-records/tree/master/invenio_rdm_records/resources/serializers/csl

Figure 2 User interface for submitting software deposit in InvenioRDM

Figure 3 User interface for the metadata record in InvenioRDM

Progress by aspect:

- Archive: 80% (missing launch on Zenodo and scale to production levels)
- Reference: 80% (missing launch on Zenodo and scale to production levels)
- Describe: 90% (missing to launch new software fields in Zenodo)
- Cite: 90% (missing CFF as export format, support in GitHub integration)

Next steps:

- Implement the automatic archiving of software in SWH, see Github issues 20³⁵ and 21³⁶

9.3.1.2 Dataverse

Work done:

- Updated technical requirements and specifications³⁷ (WIP).
- Work on DANS Deposit form³⁸:
 - User login to the form (AAI, Google only in BETA).
 - Specific SWH and Dataverse form fields (e.g., software authors and dataset authors).

³⁵ <https://github.com/inveniosoftware/invenio-swh/issues/20>

³⁶ <https://github.com/inveniosoftware/invenio-swh/issues/21>

³⁷ <https://wiki.eduuni.fi/display/cscRDIcollaboration/Dataverse++SWH+SPECS>

³⁸ <https://swh.dansdemo.nl/>

- Deposit status feedback in the form.
- User form-documentation (WIP).
- Installed demo Dataverse³⁹ instance.
- Work on DANS transformation Service⁴⁰:
 - Transform form-data into ATOM/CodeMeta payload for SWH SWORD deposit.
 - Transform form-data into Dataverse native JSON payload to deposit to Dataverse.
- Work on DANS packaging API⁴¹ (rule-engine):
 - Deposit relevant software-related metadata to SWH (SWORD, metadata-only), including the Dataverse PID/DOI.
 - Deposit relevant data(set) related data and metadata to Dataverse, including the SWHID for citation, which is visible on the record page in Dataverse.

Figure 4 User interface of the DataVerse-DANS prototype for the archival of the software artifacts in Software Heritage

Figure 5 User interface for finding results including software in the DataVerse-Dans prototype

³⁹ <https://dataverse.eosc.dansdemo.nl/>

⁴⁰ <https://transformer.labs.dans.knaw.nl/docs>

⁴¹ <https://packaging.labs.dans.knaw.nl/docs>

Progress by aspect:

- Archive: 80%
- Reference: 80%
- Describe: 80%
- Cite: 50%

Next steps:

- WIP on DANS Packaging API:
 - Evaluate other 'Origin' types besides 'git'.
- WIP on DANS Deposit form:
 - Preserve/save deposit form-state.
 - Improve documentation

9.3.2 Publishers

9.3.2.1 Dagstuhl

Work done:

- Back-end API (php-laravel-based) interacting with SWH Data Model⁴².
- The API utilises all the endpoints required to propagate through the SWH tree model as well as triggering repositories archiving.
- Automation functionality for:
 - Archiving (base URL as supported by SWH)
 - Tracking archiving status (utilising `save_request_status`, `visit_status`, etc.)
 - Propagating/Traversal the SWH Data Model to hit specific nodes based on the given repository URL.
- Archiving and Propagation techniques respect the specific repositories endpoints (or paths), e.g., branches, (sub-)directories, files, pulls, releases.
 - These endpoints are defined in the full URL given by the respective repo (just copy the browser URL).
 - Currently supported list can be found here⁴³.
 - Integration to Dagstuhl Submission Server (i.e. during papers submissions with relevant repositories).
- A Front-end version where the relevant SWHIDs are rendered to.
- SPECS Functional requirements.
- SPECS Functional specifications (Bullet points: 1, 2, 3, 4, & 6).
- Building a public app to show some use-cases for the Archive Pillar for testing and feedback.
- Documentation of the LZI-SWH API.
- Integration of relevant SWHIDs (Currently: Directory & Content Contexts based on the given URL) to LaTeX marco snippets that are compiled and shown on document
- Automation of SWHIDs integration for SW referencing on documents.
- Integration to Dagstuhl Submission Server (i.e. during papers submissions with relevant repositories).
- Hosting in a public server for testing and feedback.
- A user-friendly interface to deal with `codeMeta.json` and `MetaData` conversions.
- `CodeMeta.json` generator (export mode).
- `CodeMeta.json` editor (import mode).
- `CodeMeta.json` conversions to other metadata schemes:
 - bibTex
 - bibLaTex
 - DataCite
- Generating SWH-XML format (with `CodeMeta`) for `MetaData`-only deposit.
- Validations of `CodeMeta` and the other Schemes.

⁴² https://docs.softwareheritage.org/_images/swh-merkle-dag.svg

⁴³ https://jira.eduuni.fi/secure/attachment/56572/56572_URLs.txt

- A user-friendly interface to deal with codeMeta.json and citation formats.
- CodeMeta.json conversions (from import/export mode) to citation formats:
 - bibTex
 - bibLaTex
- Validations of CodeMeta and the other Schemes.

Figure 6 User interface for submitting software artifacts alongside the article

Figure 7 An article example with the reference to software materials using the SWHID

Progress by aspect:

- Archive: 95%
- Reference: 95%
- Describe: 50%
- Cite: 50%

Next steps:

- Bug fixes, feedback, enhancements.
- Adding support for JSON-LD compatibility in the import mode.
- SWORD v2 Client.
- Depositing MetaData to SWH.
- SPECS Functional specifications (Bullet point: 5).
- Integration to the internal Dagstuhl system and getting feedback from users.
- Publishing Description formats on DROPS (Dagstuhl Publication Server) unless SWH will publish Description data on their UI.
- Adding citation formats to bibliography.
- Retrievability of citation formats.
- Integration to Dagstuhl internal system.
- Provide guidelines/best practices regarding citation of software and how to use these citation formats.

9.3.2.2 Episciences

Work done:

- API to retrieve metadata from Software Heritage: authors can add a source code (by specifying the SWHID) to their paper submission
- Reviewers have access to the source code in the peer-reviewing form following the permalink SWHID
- The corresponding SWHID is displayed on the journal’s publication record and an iframe displays the software source code available in Software Heritage
- Sandbox already available for testing.
- Documentation available here⁴⁴:

Figure 8 User interface for submitting linked materials in Episciences, including data and software

⁴⁴ <https://doc.episciences.org/en/welcome/>

Figure 9 User interface for metadata record on Episciences including an iFrame to browse code in SWH

Progress by aspect:

- Archive: N/A (the source code is already archived on Software Heritage)
- Reference: 100%
- Describe: 40%
- Cite: 20%

Next steps:

- An API to retrieve metadata from scholarly repository so that authors can add a source code (by specifying the HalId) to their paper submission
- Export format in BibTeX with software source code reference

9.3.3 Aggregators

9.3.3.1 swMATH

Work done:

- Code already developed to trigger save code endpoint API for GitHub repositories
- swMATH has selected and provided information describing the SageMath software
- Mapping between swMATH metadata and CodeMeta vocabularies
- swMATH has solved with the SWH development team user accounts issues
- swMATH succeeded to deposit an example of metadata with the “only-deposit” endpoint of the SWH API SWH on the staging server
- swMATH has exposed the SWHID for the SageMath software
- swMATH has selected and provided articles citing the SageMath software
- Mapping between swMATH metadata and CodeMeta vocabularies
- swMATH has solved with the SWH development team user accounts issues
- swMATH succeeded to deposit an example of metadata with the “metadata-only-deposit” endpoint of the SWH API SWH on the staging server

Figure 10 User interface for the metadata record of a software entry on swMATH

Progress by aspect:

- Archive: 90%
- Reference: 100%
- Describe: 80%
- Cite: 40%

Next steps:

- Identify the repositories containing links to these forges and trigger the archival of their source code:
 - Gitlab public platform
 - open repositories deployed on local Gitlab servers
 - Bitbucket platform
 - Other git servers
- swMATH will deposit the metadata of other software after the Beta release
- Solve potential issues regarding copyrights aspects for some software
- Provide information regarding software version if possible
- Make other mappings available (DataCite, BibTex, CSL, etc.)

9.3.3.2 OpenAIRE

Work done:

- The workflow that triggers the archival of (already included in OpenAIRE) software entities in SWH was merged in our beta branch⁴⁵
- It was deployed as part of the OpenAIRE Graph Beta update (during October), limiting the number of software repositories from OpenAIRE that we searched in the SWH API to 5,000
- Software entities in the OpenAIRE Graph were adjusted to hold retrieved SWH IDs.
- "Save code now" requests are submitted to the SWH API when a software is missing from SWH, or last visit time was prior to a given time period (1 year in our current deployment)
- SWH IDs are exposed (when available) through the Beta RDGraph Explore portal⁴⁶
- SWH IDs are exposed through the OpenAIRE's API⁴⁷ (see `pid` property of the response)

⁴⁵ <https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/beta/dhp-workflows/dhp-swh>

⁴⁶ <https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu/search/software?pid=swh:1:snp:29010d1cc53b077b3f13e96cc12aeceb89c4fa1a>

⁴⁷ <https://api-beta.openaire.eu/search/software?openaireSoftwareID=openaire::072103d7bb3f3ccd60b72b470adcbef6&format=json>

- The Beta RDGraph Explore portal⁴⁸ allows searching with SWHID
- Initial investigation on how exchange software metadata between OpenAIRE and SWH
- Software entities can be exported using Bibtext through the RDGraph Explore portal⁴⁹ using the "Cite" button on the top of the page

Figure 11 User interface for a software entry in OpenAire

Figure 12 User interface for a search view in OpenAire

Progress by aspect:

- Archive: 90%
- Reference: 95%
- Describe: 15%
- Cite: 25%

Next steps:

- Enable more efficient retrieval of SWH IDs, i.e., for all software entities in the OpenAIRE Graph
- Planning to add more context in the link pointing to the respective SWH software page
- Start implementing the workflow to exchange software metadata between OpenAIRE Graph and SWH

⁴⁸ <https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu/search/find/research-outcomes?f0=q&fv0=swh%253A1%253Asnp%253A815ab3cd2c8fdf18b7eac294b8a08b09393cba89%2520>

⁴⁹ <https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu/search/software?pid=swh:1:snp:815ab3cd2c8fdf18b7eac294b8a08b09393cba89>

- Enrich software metadata so as BibTex export would be more complete (related to the previous point⁵⁰)
- Investigation on exporting using codemeta.json format

9.3.4 Next steps for RSAC component

The FAIRCORE4EOSC RSAC component has made significant progress in aligning with the EOSC SIRS report and the 2021 SIRS report. The beta release, scheduled for the end of November 2023, represents a key milestone in integrating research software into the scholarly ecosystem. Across scholarly repositories, publishers, and aggregators, the project has achieved notable advancements, including integration with the Software Heritage archive and adherence to the CodeMeta standard.

As of November 21st, each sub-component (InvenioRDM, Dans-Dataverse, Dagstuhl, Episciences, swMATH, OpenAIRE) has demonstrated substantial progress, with detailed requirements and progress updates. The iterative development process, including a sprint organised by INRIA in October 2023, ensures functionalities align with specifications.

Looking ahead, the project plans to collect user feedback post-beta release and iterate on further developments. The commitment to the SIRS report's vision remains strong, and the tools developed under WP6 contribute significantly to reshaping scholarly communication.

⁵⁰ <https://jira.eduuni.fi/browse/CSCFC4EREQ-493>

10 Integrating FAIRCORE4EOSC components with the EOSC Core

The EOSC is a long-term initiative from the European Commission (EC) supporting research and Open Science in Europe. The aim of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project is to develop and realise new EOSC-Core components supporting a FAIR EOSC, addressing gaps identified in the SRIA.

During proposal preparation a high-level architecture diagram was developed showing the FAIRCORE4EOSC components (green boxes) in relation to the existing EOSC-Core (yellow boxes), see Figure #.

Figure 13 Architecture overview of the new FAIRCORE4EOSC components in relation to the EOSC-Core

The current EOSC-Core platform has been developed through the EOSC Future project⁵¹. At the beginning of this year (i.e. 2023) the EC launched a procurement to acquire the EOSC-Core as managed services (i.e. Lot 1). In November 2023 the EC announced the winner of the Lot 1 - Core Federation Services for the EOSC EU Node⁵². The handover of the EOSC-Core platform from EOSC Future to the winners of the EOSC Procurement Lot 1 has an impact on the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. This impact is addressed in section 10.1. Figure 14 is lacking the details on how the FAIRCORE4EOSC components are planned to be connected the EOSC Core, this will be described in section 10.2.

10.1 Impact of the EOSC Procurement

The aim of FAIRCORE4EOSC is to extend the EOSC-Core with new components supporting FAIR. As a result of the EOSC Procurement a transition of the contractual agreement to operate the EOSC-Core is planned with the EC as new contract-owner. The responsibility to operate the EOSC-core will be handed over from EOSC Future to the winners of EOSC Procurement Lot 1. Due to this transition, it became uncertain for the FAIRCORE4EOSC project how, to what purpose and under which conditions to integrate and offer the FAIRCORE4EOSC components as components of the EOSC Node at EC level. The handover of the EOSC-

⁵¹ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

⁵² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/commission-announces-winners-eosc-procurement>

Core from EOSC Future to the EC and the winners of the EOSC Procurement Lot1 is planned in the first half 2024.

Because of this uncertainty, the FAIRCORE4EOSC project will adopt a dual approach:

1. Offering the components as services through the EOSC-Exchange
2. Expanding the EOSC-Core and offering the components as EOSC-Core capabilities

Approach 2 requires an engagement with the EC and the winners of the EOSC Procurement Lot 1 to discuss the inclusion of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components in the EOSC Node. The handover of the EOSC-Core from EOSC Future to the EC and the winners of the EOSC Procurement Lot1 is planned in the first half 2024.

10.2 Integrating with the EOSC Core

In this section a more detailed description will be provided on how the FAIRCORE4EOSC components can be connected to the EOSC Core, either as onboarded services into the EOSC Exchange or as new components of the EOSC Core. To explain the connections to the different capabilities of the EOSC Node the diagram Figure # is used. To make services and resources available through EOSC, a service needs at least to be onboarded to the EOSC-Exchange. At the time of this report, integrating with the EOSC-Core is not mandatory, it is considered optional and depends on the component and local context of the component service provider.

Figure 14 Diagram showing the connections from a Provider perspective to the EOSC-Core

For each of the EOSC-Core capabilities the integration with the EOSC-Core will be described according to the dual approach.

10.2.1 Onboarding services into the EOSC Service Catalogue

The EOSC Service Catalogue is a component of the overall EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace⁵³ (EOSC-Exchange). It is a database of records of providers, services, and external catalogues which is compatible with

⁵³ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

the EOSC Profiles specifications. The aim of the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace is to make services and research products discoverable and accessible through EOSC.

Table 42 Onboarding services into the EOSC Service Catalogue

Onboarding in	Description
EOSC-Exchange	<p>The aim of onboarding FAIRCORE4EOSC components into the EOSC-Exchange is to offer the components as services to the EOSC research communities. To onboard the components into the EOSC-Exchange the FAIRCORE4EOSC component providers need to go through the service onboarding process as described on the EOSC Portal Providers Hub and need to comply to the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOSC Profiles for Providers and Services⁵⁴ • EOSC Exchange inclusion criteria⁵⁵ • EOSC Maturity levels⁵⁶
EOSC-Core	<p>At the time of this report there are no criteria defined to extend and/or to connect to the EOSC Node. The handover of the EOSC-Core from EOSC Future to the EC and the winners of the EOSC Procurement Lot1 is planned in the first half 2024.</p>

10.2.3 Joining the EOSC AAI Federation

The EOSC AAI Federation enables Service Providers (that are part of a Community AAI or an Infrastructure Proxy) to deliver resources to research communities and to facilitate individual researchers to access resources. This is made possible by allowing users to leverage their institutional, community and eIDAS-compliant digital identities (or any other trust Identity Provider the Service Provider may allow).

Table 43 Joining the EOSC AAI Federation

Onboarding in	Description
EOSC-Exchange	<p>The aim of joining the EOSC Federated AAI is to allow users from the EOSC community domain federated access to the FAIRCORE4EOSC components. EOSC-Exchange services are not integrated with the EOSC Node Core Infrastructure Proxy but the EOSC Federated AAI by connecting to an RI, e-infrastructure or NREN offered Infrastructure Proxy which is a member of eduGAIN or of the EOSC AAI Federation. To allow EOSC federated access the FAIRCORE4EOSC components need to be integrated with an:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure Proxy which is compliant to the AARC Blueprint^{57,58} • Infrastructure Proxy provisioned through an eduGAIN member⁵⁹ • Or Infrastructure Proxy which is a member the EOSC AAI Federation⁶⁰
EOSC-Core	<p>To provide a Single-Sign-On experience for users, to allow users to only login once within the EOSC Node, EOSC Node components need to be integrated with Infrastructure Proxy of the EOSC Node.</p>

⁵⁴ https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-providers-hub/what-are-eosc-profiles#Provider_Profiles

⁵⁵ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Exchange+inclusion+criteria>

⁵⁶ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Future+Glossary#EOSCFutureGlossary-TRL>

⁵⁷ <https://aarc-project.eu/architecture/>

⁵⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3672785>

⁵⁹ <https://technical.edugain.org/status>

⁶⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Wierenga, K., Johansson, L., Kanellopoulos, C. et al., *EOSC Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture AAI Task Force (TF)*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8702>

10.2.3 Connecting to the EOSC Monitoring

The EOSC Monitoring service checks the status, availability, and reliability of EOSC resources both in the EOSC-Core and EOSC-Exchange. It supports the ability to monitor and observe EOSC resource availability as a measure of resource quality. Basic monitoring is based on a service endpoint or web page accessibility. Advanced monitoring is based on special probes developed as part of integration with the resource.

Table 44 Connecting to the EOSC Monitoring

Onboarding in	Description
EOSC-Exchange	<p>By allowing the EOSC Monitoring service⁶¹ to monitor the FAIRCORE4EOSC components, EOSC users can see and assess the status, availability and reliability of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components. After the onboarding of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components into the EOSC-Exchange, the components are monitored at a basic level by default. To improve the quality of monitoring beyond the basic level, FAIRCORE4EOSC component providers can select advanced monitoring options to further integrate with the EOSC Monitoring service. To do so, the FAIRCORE4EOSC providers must follow the <i>EOSC Monitoring: Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines</i>⁶², which offers 5 integration options:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitor an Onboarded Service 2. Monitor an Infrastructure. 3. Integrate External Monitoring service. 4. Combine Results of existing ARGO Tenants 5. Third-party services exploiting EOSC Monitoring data <p>Advanced monitoring of EOSC Exchange services is optional; basic monitoring is enabled by default.</p>
EOSC-Core	<p>EOSC-Core monitoring is mandatory for EOSC-Core components and are monitored through the EOSC Core Monitoring service⁶³. The EOSC-Core monitoring service is based on the same technology as the EOSC Monitoring service, therefore refer to the <i>EOSC Monitoring: Architecture Interoperability Guidelines</i> to integrate the new core components to the EOSC-Core Monitoring service. EOSC Core providers also need to comply with the <i>EOSC SMS Service Availability and Continuity Management</i> processes.</p>

10.2.4 Connecting to the EOSC Helpdesk

EOSC Helpdesk acts as a single point of contact for all EOSC customers for requesting help, support and other requests. It provides ticket management and allows to track the inquiries related to EOSC services, resources, and projects. It enables multiple support units, collection of incident statistics and facilitates SLA's, a personal dashboard, issue history and current status of submitted requests.

Table 45 Connecting to the EOSC Helpdesk

Onboarding in	Description
EOSC-Exchange	<p>By integrating the FAIRCORE4EOSC component providers' own support channels with the EOSC Helpdesk, providers can provide a single contact point for support to EOSC users. To connect the support channels of the FAIRCORE4EOSC providers to the EOSC Helpdesk, the providers need to follow the <i>EOSC Helpdesk: Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines</i>⁶⁴, which offers 4 integration options:</p>

⁶¹ <https://monitoring.eosc-portal.eu/>

⁶² <https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/guidelines/eosc.40f7b33103fdaa1d384a477358acedcc>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8333926>

⁶³ <https://monitoring-core.eosc-portal.eu/>

⁶⁴ <https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/guidelines/eosc.fa941127b3ace6ad90b2695db8d07531>

Onboarding in	Description
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Direct usage 2. Ticket redirection 3. Full integration 4. Dedicated instance <p>EOSC users can contact the support channels of the providers via the <i>Helpdesk</i> link on the EOSC Exchange landing page of the service; more advanced integration options are optional.</p>
EOSC-Core	The support channel of the EOSC-Core is the EOSC Helpdesk. Therefore, when FAIRCORE4EOSC components are integrated with the EOSC-Core, the FAIRCORE4EOSC component providers need to be integrated with the EOSC Helpdesk ⁶⁵ and need to comply with the <i>EOSC SMS Incident and Service Request Management</i> processes.

10.2.5 Connecting to the EOSC Order Management System

The Order Management System manages orders for services made through the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace⁶⁶. It collects customer/user requests with relevant data and passes these to the providers of the services. It avoids the need for the user to go to separate services' ordering pages and the need to get familiar with different ordering workflows, by providing a uniform ordering interface for multiple services.

Table 46 Connecting to the EOSC Order Management System

Onboarding in	Description
EOSC-Exchange	Depending on how the FAIRCORE4EOSC components are offered to users and research communities, the FAIRCORE4EOSC component providers can integrate with the EOSC Order Management System. For FAIRCORE4EOSC components which are offered as free services, because no registration is required (or because they can be used upon registration), no ordering is required and therefore do not need to be integrated with the EOSC Ordering System. FAIRCORE4EOSC components that require ordering because the component requires configuration and/or resources to be allocated, need to configure ordering through the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace. By default the FAIRCORE4EOSC components can be ordered via the <i>Order URL</i> which can be located on the Details page of the EOSC Exchange landing page of the service. More advanced ordering capabilities are provided through the EOSC Order Management System. To connect to the EOSC Order Management System FAIRCORE4EOSC providers need to follow the <i>EOSC Order Management System Interoperability Guideline</i> ⁶⁷ .
EOSC-Core	Requests for EOSC-Core components and/or capabilities are handled through the EOSC Helpdesk and tracked through the EOSC Order Management System. Therefore, when FAIRCORE4EOSC components are integrated with the EOSC-Core, the FAIRCORE4EOSC components providers need to be integrated with the EOSC Order Management System (see <i>EOSC Order Management System Interoperability Guideline</i> ⁶⁸), and need to comply with the <i>EOSC SMS Service Order and Customer Relationship Management</i> processes.

10.2.6 Making FAIRCORE4EOSC research assets discoverable

One of the main aims of EOSC is to build the *Web of FAIR data and services*. The current way of building the Web of FAIR data is to make research assets (e.g. publications, data, software, training material, interoperability guidelines) discoverable through the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace. To make research

⁶⁵ <https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/guidelines/eosc.fa941127b3ace6ad90b2695db8d07531>

⁶⁶ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

⁶⁷ <https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/guidelines/eosc.c1efa7ced16602193efe80952ab3a6c7>

⁶⁸ <https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/guidelines/eosc.c1efa7ced16602193efe80952ab3a6c7>

assets discoverable through EOSC, the services themselves must be onboarded as data sources and allow the harvesting of metadata records from research assets stored on a data source to onboard the research assets into the Research Product catalogue.

Table 47 Making FAIRDORE4EOSC research assets discoverable

Onboarding in	Description
EOSC-Exchange	Many of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components (e.g. MSCR, DTR, RAiD, RSAC) are built to register and maintain research assets (e.g. metadata schemas, crosswalks, data types, information about research projects and research software). Therefore, these components are eligible to be onboarded as data sources to make their research assets discoverable through the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace. In the context of the EOSC, data sources are considered a special type of service. To onboard the FAIRCORE4EOSC components as data sources the components need to comply with both the inclusion criteria for services and data sources. To onboard the components as data sources, the components need to onboard the research assets as Research Products. For this, the FAIRCORE4EOSC component providers need to follow the <i>EOSC Interoperability Guidelines for Data Sources to onboard Research Products</i> ⁶⁹ .
EOSC-Core	Enabling discoverability of research assets from the EOSC-Core components is achieved via the same onboarding processes and guidelines used by Data Sources, see <i>EOSC Interoperability Guidelines for Data Sources to onboard Research Products</i> ⁷⁰ .

10.2.7 Connecting to the EOSC Accounting for Research Products

The EOSC Accounting for Research Products collects, processes and publishes usage statistics for research products from EOSC Providers, using automated and standardised scientific methods. The Service is built upon the UsageCounts service of OpenAIRE and follows the guidelines of the *COUNTER Code of Practice for e-Resources*⁷¹.

Despite many of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components being considered data sources due to their registration and management of research assets, the components are not typical data sources, except for the repositories, publishers and aggregators contributing to the RSAC developments. To allow the publication of Open Science metrics, when applicable, the FAIRCORE4EOSC component providers need to follow the *EOSC IF Interoperability Guideline for Research Products Accounting*⁷².

10.2.8 Connecting to the EOSC Accounting for Services

The EOSC-Core Accounting for Services component is a platform that is responsible for collecting, aggregating, and exchanging types of accounting metrics between different infrastructures and service providers. At time of this report there was no interoperability guideline available on how to provide usage metrics to the EOSC-Core Accounting for Services component.

Because of the heterogeneity of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components there are no default metrics to measure the usage of a service and/or resource, these need to be defined per component. Because of the lack of an interoperability guideline and because of handover of the EOSC Core from EOSC Future to the EC integration with the EOSC-Core Accounting for Service is not prioritised and considered as optional.

⁶⁹ <https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/guidelines/eosc.85412df68dd1171538a8609913fb6c71>

⁷⁰ <https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/guidelines/eosc.85412df68dd1171538a8609913fb6c71>

⁷¹ <https://www.projectcounter.org/release-5-1/>

⁷² <https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/guidelines/eosc.8a79fbaf2492ac4df3433c9288d3a8b7>

10.3 FAIRCORE4EOSC Cross-component Integration

Each FAIRCORE4EOSC component needs to provide stand-alone value, independent from connection to the EOSC-Core, or integration with other FAIRCORE4EOSC components. Further, from a project perspective it is important to leverage components and developments conducted within the project as much as possible, as was envisioned during the drafting of the proposal.

The Table 52 below provides an overview of the technical integrations planned between the FAIRCORE4EOSC components.

Table 48 FAIRCORE4EOSC Cross-component integrations

Component	Integrated with	Description of the integration
CAT	MSCR	Reuse of the MSCR/EOSC Vocabulary service to manage, list and retrieve vocabulary elements and details.
	EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy	To test the federated access and SSO with the EOSC-Core it has been integrated with the demo instance of the EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy
MSRC	DTR	Schema and Crosswalk editor leverages the data type information registered within the DTR service.
	EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy	To test the federated access and SSO with the EOSC-Core it has been integrated with the demo instance of the EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy
RAiD	PIDGraph	RAiD service assigns DataCite DOIs for RAiD records, these are automatically included within the PIDGraph
	RDGraph	Suggests possible RAiDs for research projects (and communities) aiming to facilitate EOSC users to manage and track related activities.
	EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy	To test the federated access and SSO with the EOSC-Core it is planned to be integrated with the demo instance of the EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy
PIDMR	EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy	To test the federated access and SSO with the EOSC-Core it is planned to be integrated with the demo instance of the EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy
RDGraph	RAiD	Facilitates EOSC users to manage and track related activities
EOSC Marketplace		Supports the registration of RAiD while creating a project in the Marketplace to order resources from the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace.
URN:NBN	PIDMR	Resolves the URN:NBN of Finnish and German resolvers
SWHID		Resolves SWH Identifiers
DOI		Resolves DOI's, including RAiD DOIs
Handle		Resolves Handles PIDs

Component	Integrated with	Description of the integration
ARK		Resolves ARK PIDs
ArXiv		Resolves ArXiv PIDs
InvenioRDM	SWH	A release in a software source code repository (e.g. GitHub) can be automatically archived using a Codemeta file in the source code repository. Support the creation of record from a SWHID and expose the SWHID and DOI are both on the record landing page.
DataVerse		Develop a deposit pipeline that deposits software to Software Heritage and cross-linking DOI issued by Dataverse and the SWHID issued by Software Heritage.
Dagstuhl		Automates the archival in Software Heritage of the source code of artifacts associated with research articles and exposes the corresponding SWHID on the journal's publication record.
Episciences		Source code is already archived on Software Heritage, exposes the corresponding SWHID on the journal's publication record and enables the deposit and retrieval in Software Heritage of curated metadata for software associated to publications.
swMath		Extracts references to software from research articles and trigger archival of source code known to swMATH, expose the corresponding origin (url) and SWHID and support the deposit and retrieval of metadata for the software artifacts in Software Heritage
OpenAIRE Explore		Triggers the archival of software artifacts which are already included in OpenAIRE (since they have been identified based on their mentions in research articles) but are missing in SWH. Maintain and expose the SWHIDs for all the software artefact records maintained by OpenAIRE, where applicable. Deposit missing software artefact metadata in SWH and retrieve software artefact descriptions from SWH to be included in the respective OpenAIRE records.
SHWMR		Deployment of an EOSC Run Mirror of Software Heritage to serve the EOSC community to archive the software for the EOSC-Core in Software Heritage.

Appendix 1 Overview Beta-Releases

Table 56 provides references to the beta-releases of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Components and sub-components made available at M18.

Table 49 Overview of the FAIRCORE4EOSC component beta-releases

Component	Sub-component	URL
CAT	User Interface	https://cat.argo.grnet.gr/
	API	https://api.cat.argo.grnet.gr/
RDGraph	Natural language search	https://test.darelab.athenarc.gr/text-to-sql/fc4eosc
	Impact-based search	https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu
	Community recommendation profiles	http://test.darelab.athenarc.gr/crps/
	RDGraph portals	https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu
PIDGraph	PID Graph harvesting service	https://api.datacite.org/graphql
MSCR	Backend API	https://mscr-test.rahtiapp.fi/swagger
	User Interface	https://mscr-test.rahtiapp.fi
DTR	Beta instance Corda software	http://typeregistry.lab.pidconsortium.net/
	TypeAPI REST API	http://typeapi.lab.pidconsortium.net
RAiD	API	https://api.demo.raid.org.au/swagger-ui/index.html#/raid-stable-v1
PIDMR	Metaresolver Backend	https://pidmr.lab.pidconsortium.net
	Metaresolver UI	https://pidmr.devel.argo.grnet.gr
RSAC	InvenioRDM - SWH	https://sandbox.zenodo.org/
	DataVerse - SWH	https://swh.dansdemo.nl/
	Dagstuhl - SWH	https://faircore4eosc.dagstuhl.de/
	Episciences - SWH	https://epijinfo.episciences.org/

Component	Sub-component	URL
	swMATH - SWH	https://staging.swmath.org/wiki/Sagemath
	OpenAIRE - SWH	https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu/search/software?pid=swh:1:snp:29010d1cc53b077b3f13e96cc12aeceb89c4fa1a